

Project Planning & Valuation: Fundamentals and Applications

Lecture Notes

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November 2025**

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DOI of the publication:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17566880>

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Summary

This work introduces key concepts and quantitative methods in project management and investment evaluation, designed as lecture notes for engineering students. It not only provides theoretical foundations but also demonstrates their practical applications, thereby supporting project planning, control, and financial assessment in real-world scenarios.

Chapter 1 covers the fundamentals of project management, including project definition, planning, and network-based scheduling techniques (PERT/CPM) for time and resource optimization. Chapter 2 addresses uncertainty in project management by applying probabilistic models to activity durations and critical path analysis. Chapter 3 focuses on the management and scheduling of physical resources, supported by illustrative examples. Chapter 4 presents Earned Value Management as an integrated approach for tracking project performance across scope, cost, and schedule. Chapter 5 introduces financial principles – risk, return, and the time value of money – essential for evaluating engineering investments. Finally, Chapter 6 details investment valuation methods – including Net Present Value, Payback Period, and Internal Rate of Return – and applies them to real-world case studies and company valuation exercises.

Together, these notes provide a coherent overview of project planning, execution, and economic evaluation, linking management techniques with decision-making.

Chapter 1: Project Management Fundamentals

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the fundamentals of project management, addressing the concept of project, planning, and the main tools for controlling deadlines and resources. It explains how to set objectives, structure tasks using the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS), and plan activities considering time, cost, and quality. It introduces PERT/CPM techniques, which allow to graphically representing the precedence relationships between activities, identify the critical path – the sequence that determines the minimum duration of the project – and calculate the slack that indicates the flexibility of each task. Practical examples of network construction, time calculation, and the use of Gantt charts are also shown, ending with the application of linear programming as an alternative method for optimizing planning.

1.1 The Concept of Project¹

Generally, a project can be defined as an intention that structures the future reality methodically and progressively. In the context of management techniques, a project is a set of related tasks or activities that are directed to a primary objective to be achieved within certain specifications, such as:

- Limited time to be completed
- Limited resources (workforce, equipment, raw materials)
- Limited funding

If the proposed work is a significant undertaking, it is often referred to as a program. The distinction between programs and projects follows the framework proposed in [1]. A program, the highest level of organizational complexity, can take several years to complete and may consist of interrelated projects carried out by various organizations.

An activity or task is a subdivision of a project. It generally lasts no more than a few months, and a group or organization performs it. Sub-activities may be used, if necessary, to subdivide the project into more meaningful phases.

A work package is a set of activities assigned to a single organizational unit and still falls within the project management framework.

The work package includes a description of the work to be done, when it should be started and completed, performance indicators, and specific milestones to be achieved at certain points in time.

The project management process

The main activities associated with project management are the planning, direction, and control of resources (i.e., people, equipment, and materials), including the distribution of project activities, taking into account technical constraints on cost and time.

They are also functions of project management, adapting the strategy and organizational structure to the project's specificities.

¹ Adapted from [1]

The criteria for evaluating the project management activity are based on time, cost, and quality (e.g. [1]). These criteria define three constraints that are often mutually exclusive. For example, the restriction of quality may not be satisfied in the following conditions:

- If poor communication exists between the client and the program manager, and therefore, a different perception of the restrictions
- If the project manager makes implementation mistakes, or due to incorrect specifications of the project

The restriction of cost may not be satisfied in the following conditions:

- If there are problems with the execution time
- If the work is accepted for a price lower than budgeted
- If very optimistic cost estimates are made, they may not reflect the inefficiencies that arise during implementation

The time constraints may not be satisfied in the following conditions:

- If the resources are not available when required
- If the design specification is changed during the period of implementation

1.2 Project Planning²

Project planning begins with a clear definition of the project's purpose and objectives. This step is crucial as it provides a clear direction for the project and aids in the efficient allocation of resources.

What follows is the technical definition of the project (i.e., the work to be performed), specifying the duration, the task sequence, the estimated resource requirements, and the costs. It is also necessary to fix responsibility, define information and decision channels, and establish procedures to control the project.

Fixing the target of the project

When we do not know where we want to go, any direction will do. To minimize uncertainty, the target's fixation is the first step in planning. So, the target should be defined precisely and specified based on its usefulness to the end user. Specifying the target based on its usefulness to the end user helps bring the project to market, avoiding impractical projects.

To set the target, we start with a general purpose, such as building a house. In discussions with other project participants, for example, with the client, a more precise specification of the target emerges, such as building a two-story house with eight rooms.

By actively participating in the definition of a consensus-based, precise, and specific target, the project manager plays a key role in ensuring that the target is realistic and achievable within the available resources and time.

² Adapted form [1]

Setting goals

Goals serve as guiding principles for the project's working groups, providing a roadmap for their tasks. They are instrumental in ensuring that the project's target is achieved.

The target is divided into tasks to be implemented by project team working groups, and the objectives are specified to uniquely contribute to achieving the target. If we set the time available for the task and the resources allocated, there is a clearly defined purpose.

The definition of objectives must be accompanied by complementary information related to the following topics:

- Activities necessary to achieve the objective
- Duration of activities
- Physical resources needed to implement activities
- Budget for implementation of activities

The key factors associated with the existence of a good dismembered structure of the work are the following:

- To allow the activities to be developed independently
- To make them manageable in size
- To give authority so that the program can be conducted effectively
- To monitor and measure the state of the program
- To provide the necessary resources

In operational terms, the project planning materializes in the following elements:

- The master plan of the project
- The technical organization of the project (WBS – Work Breakdown Structure)
- The implementation plan of the activities
- The plan for the use of the resources
- The project budget

Master plan of the project

The master plan of the project is a document that identifies:

- The purpose (i.e., the target) and the project objectives
- The organizational form adopted, the definition of responsibilities, and the hierarchical dependence
- The circuits of information and decision
- The coding system of the activities
- The process of accountability and its periodicity
- Participation of the project in sub-projects and the interconnection between the different sub-projects
- The form of management adopted

Technical organization of the project

The Technical Organigram (i.e., the Work Breakdown Structure) is a representation of the project's elements at successively more detailed levels. It may be presented in graphical or list form. The project objectives are divided into elements to provide a more disaggregated view and, in probabilistic terms, ensure the identification of all project activities, even the smallest.

As an instrument of communication between the project team and the outside organization, it must be designed with a level of segregation that allows integrating project activities, controlling their costs, and assigning responsibilities – to team members and departments responsible for resource allocation.

Sequence of execution, duration of activities, and establishing the resources needed

After formulating the Technical Organigram, we must establish the sequence of the activities. In establishing the sequence of implementation, we identify, for each activity, the activities immediately preceding it that must be completed before the start of the activity.

From the logical sequence of activities, a graph can be constructed representing the connections between activities, known as the PERT/CPM network.

After establishing the execution sequence, we begin estimating the time required for each activity.

1.3 Fundamentals of PERT/CPM Networks³

Modern project management techniques emerged in the late 50s under two acronyms: PERT (Program Evaluation and Review Technique) and CPM (Critical Path Method). Although they were developed separately, the theoretical foundations of PERT and CPM are essentially the same.

The success of these techniques is based on their ability to reduce the time required to implement large, highly complex projects and to control costs and resources. These techniques present the project in graphic form, with its individual activities, so that attention is drawn to the activities critical to completing the project.

For the purpose of building the PERT/CPM network, it is assumed that the activities are defined by events or milestones that mark the beginning, middle, and end of the action. The activities are also time and resource-consuming.

In project management, two types of networks have been used: the type (i, j) (Activity-on-Arrow) and the type Xi (Activity-on-Node), which we describe next.

1.3.1 Networks of type (i, j)

These networks consist of activities, events, and interdependent relationships. Arrows and circles represent the activities.

The early event of an activity is called the preceding node or tail. The event of completion of the activity is called the succeeding node or head.

³ Adapted from [1]

The representation of events and activities is managed by a dependency rule that requires that an activity that depends on another activity be shown emerging from the head of the activity it depends on. No activity can be initiated until the event of its tail is realized, i.e., until all the activities preceding the same chain are completed.

In networks of the type (i, j), fictitious activities are often used, as they require neither material resources nor time.

There are two types of fictitious activities: identity-based and logical.

There are situations in which two activities share the same points of departure and arrival. These situations should be avoided by introducing fictitious activities of identity.

To illustrate this situation, let us consider a straightforward example: preparing coffee by mixing boiling water with ground coffee (adapted from [1]). This project consists of three activities: two that can start at the same time, related to preparing the components (boiling water and grinding coffee), and the third, mixing the two components after they are ready. This set of activities can be represented as shown in the following figure:

To represent this sequence of activities in a more elucidative way (associating a unique pair of nodes to each activity), we can use the following alternative that is built with the help of a fictitious activity of identity, between nodes 2 and 3:

In this case, it is easier to illustrate that the two initial activities are independent and that they can end at different times.

The fictitious logical activities arise in situations of the type C depends on A, while D depends on both A and B, as illustrated in the following figure:

To interpret this figure, we can start by noting that activity C can start after the event represented by node 2 occurs. In node 2, activity A converges; therefore, the event associated with node 2 is the conclusion of A.

In turn, activity D can start after the event at node three occurs. However, at node 3, two arrows converge, one representing activity B and the other representing a fictitious

activity beginning at node 2, where activity A ends. Therefore, node 3 represents the point in time when both activities A and B are terminated.

Thus, we conclude that activity C can start when activity A is completed, but activity D can only start after both A and B are completed.

1.3.2 Networks of type Xi

The networks of type Xi are defined by activities represented by boxes and dependency relations represented by arrows. These networks do not require events or fictitious activities, but they often give rise to larger, more complex networks (e.g. [1]). These networks are built from elementary relationships such as those illustrated next:

End-Start:

Start-Start:

End-End:

Example

The following table shows the set of activities for a project, along with their precedence relationships (adapted from [1]). The networks of type (i, j) and type Xi that reflect these relationships are also presented next.

Activities	Precedences
A	
B	A
C	B
D	B
E	D
F	C, E
G	E
H	E
I	F, G, H
J	I

Network (i, j)

Network Xi

We can verify that these networks represent the sequence of activity implementation, reflecting the project's given precedence relationships. For this purpose, we will analyze the network (i, j) next.

Node 1 signals the start of the project. In this node, only activity A starts because it is the only one with an empty list in the precedence table. Activity A ends at node 2, where activity B can begin. That is, B can only begin after A is completed. In the precedence table, this relationship is translated to show activity A in the list of B.

Activity B ends at node 3, where activities C and D can start. In the precedence table, both the C list and the D list include activity B.

Activity E starts at node four, where activity D ends. That is, activity E can only start after the completion of D. In the precedence table, this information is represented by listing D before E.

Activity F starts at node six, where two arrows converge: one that represents the completion of C and another that is a logical fictitious activity that is linked to node 5, where activity E ends. Therefore, F can only start when C and E are completed. In the list of precedences, this relationship is characterized by including the two precedences C and E in the list of F.

Activities G and H start at node 5, where activity E ends. Therefore, the lists of activities G and H have the precedence of E.

Activity I starts at node 8, where three arrows converge: two represent activities F and G, and the third is a fictitious activity of identity that is linked to node 7, which marks the conclusion of H. Therefore, activity I has precedences F, G, and H, as shown in its precedence list.

Finally, activity J starts at node nine, where activity I terminates. Therefore, activity J has only activity I as a precedent. Node 10 represents the event that signals the project's completion.

1.4 Network Construction

The process of constructing (i, j) type networks is illustrate next, but the process of constructing Xi networks is identical. To construct a PERT/CPM network, a table listing the activity codes and the precedence list of activities is used.

The construction of the (i, j) type network begins by drawing the node corresponding to the start of the project. Next, we draw arrows for the activities that can be started at that node, i.e., those that have the precedence list empty.

As the activities are being drawn, the codes are scratched from both the activity list and the precedence list. The activities at each stage that can be started are those with the precedence list empty.

To start a new activity, it is necessary to draw a node that marks the beginning and the end of the activities that precede it.

If there are no more activities to introduce, a final node is drawn, marking the end of the last introduced activities and the project.

Example 1.4.1

Let's illustrate the process of building a PERT/CPM network considering the project with the activities detailed in the following table (adapted from [1]).

Activities	Precedences
A	
B	
C	
D	
E	A
F	A
G	E
H	F, G
I	B
J	C
K	D
L	H
M	K
N	I, L

The construction of the PERT/CPM network of type (i, j) begins with introducing the node that signals the start of the project (i.e., the start of the time count). Next, the activities with an empty precedence list – A, B, C, and D – are introduced. This is the first step, which we mark on the left side of the table.

To start the second step, we have to cross out the activities listed on the left and right sides of the table, as shown next. After striking out the activities introduced in the first step, we identify the activities whose precedence list is now empty. These activities are E, F, and also I, J, and K.

Activities E and F are preceded by activity A. To introduce these activities, we first need to introduce a node to signal the conclusion of A, in which E and F can also start.

To introduce I, J, and K, we must first introduce the nodes that signal the conclusions of B, C, and D, in which I, J, and K can start, respectively.

Moreover, now we repeat the process.

1	A	
	B	
	C	
	D	
2	E	A
	F	A
	G	E
2	H	F, G
	I	B
	J	C
	K	D
	L	H
	M	K
N	I, L	

To identify the third step, we must first cross out the activities of the second step on both sides of the table: first E and F, then I, J, and K.

After crossing out the activities of the second step, we find that in the third step, we can introduce activities G and M, after E and K, respectively. To do this, we must also introduce two nodes that signal the end of E and the end of K, where G and M can start, respectively.

1	A	
	B	
	C	
	D	
2	E	A
	F	A
3-	G	E
	H	F, G
2	I	B
	J	C
	K	D
3-	L	H
	M	K
	N	I, L

The fourth step is identified by striking out G and M from the previous step. We verify that we are now going to introduce activity H. Since this activity has two precedents, F and G, we can introduce a node that signals the time limit for completing F and G, after which activity H can start.

1	A	
	B	
	C	
	D	
2	E	A
	F	A
3-	G	E
	H	F, G
2	I	B
	J	C
	K	D
3-	L	H
	M	K
	N	I, L

In the fifth step, we introduce activity L after H.

1	A	
	B	
	C	
	D	
2	E	A
	F	A
3-	G	E
	H	F, G
2	I	B
	J	C
	K	D
5-	L	H
	M	K
3-	N	I, L

In the sixth step, we introduce activity N, which has two precedences, I and L. To do this, we introduce a node where I and L converge, which signals the completion of these activities and the beginning of N.

1	A	
	B	
	C	
	D	
2	E	A
	F	A
3-	G	E
	H	F, G
2	I	B
	J	C
	K	D
5-	L	H
	M	K
3-	N	I, L

As we have already introduced all the activities, we completed the network by adding a node that signals the project's completion time, at which all activities without successors end.

Example 1.4.2

The activities of a project and their precedence relations are shown in the table below (adapted from [1]):

A	
B	
C	
D	B
E	B
F	C
G	A, D
H	A, D
I	F
J	E, H, I

Present the PERT/CPM networks of type (i, j) and type Xi.

Solution

The solution to this problem is presented below without a detailed explanation, as in the previous problem. The objective is to make the solution available for verification after you try to design the networks autonomously, following the process described in the previous problem.

To assist you in the process, the steps involved and the activities to be introduced at each step are identified next: [Step 1] A, B, C; [Step 2] D, E, F; [Step 3] G, H, I, and [Step 4] J.

Network (i, j)

Network Xi

1.5. Critical Activities and Analysis of Slack

Having established the network of activities, a calendar is created with the initiation and completion dates for each activity to minimize the project's duration.

As nodes mark where activities can start and terminate, we first determine the earliest and latest occurrence times for each node to determine the schedule of activities.

The Earliest Time (ET) and the Latest Time (LT) define the temporal limits of the events represented in the node. When these times are equal, the node is said to be critical.

1.5.1 Determination of the Earliest Time of Occurrence

In the case of the events (nodes), we specify the Earliest Time and the Latest Time of occurrence. For the activities, we define times associated with the start: Earliest Starting Time (EST) and Latest Starting Time (LST); and with the conclusion: Earliest Conclusion Time (ECT) and Latest Conclusion Time (LCT).

The earliest time of occurrence of a node (ET) is the earliest time to initiate its succeeding activities (EST). The value of the earliest time of occurrence of a node (ET) is determined by the highest value of the earliest completion time (ECT), from all the activities that can be concluded at that node (e.g. [2]):

Earliest completion time of activity Xij

At node j, no activity can be initiated unless all previous ones are completed.

To determine the earliest and latest times of occurrence of the nodes, we first determine the earliest times of occurrence.

The earliest times are determined by starting with the first node and assigning it a value of zero. The earliest times of the following nodes are determined from the earliest times of the preceding nodes and the durations of the antecedent activities.

Example

The network (i, j), shown in the following figure, includes information on the durations of the activities and also presents the earliest times for the nodes.

The determination of the earliest times of the nodes (ET) begins by assigning the value 0 to the first node. The value in node two is obtained by adding the duration of activity A to the value of ET_1 . In node three, we first evaluate the earliest completion times

(ECT) of B and C, then choose the highest value. We have to choose the highest value because activity D can start only when both B and C are completed. In node 4, the ET_4 value is obtained by adding the activity D duration to the ET_3 value.

1.5.2 Determination of the Latest Time of Occurrence

The latest time of occurrence of a node (LT) is the latest completion time of its previous activities (LCT).

The value of the latest time of occurrence of a node is determined by the smallest of the latest starting times (LST) from all activities that start from the node (e.g. [2]):

$$LT_i = \min_j \{LT_j - d_{ij}\}$$

Latest starting time of activity Xij

At node i, no activity can be completed after the start of any subsequent activity.

The latest time is determined by starting from the last node and assigning to it the same value as the earliest time, which represents the project's duration. The latest times of the previous nodes are determined from the latest time of the following nodes and the duration of the following activities.

Example

The network (i, j), shown in the following figure, includes information on the duration of the activities and presents the earliest and latest dates for each node.

The determination of the latest times of the nodes (LT) starts at node 6, with $LT_6 = ET_6 = 6$. The value of LT_3 , in node 3, is obtained by subtracting the duration of activity D from LT_6 . In node 2, we first evaluate the latest starting times of B and C, then select the minimum. We have to choose the lowest value because activity A cannot terminate after the start of B or C. In the first node, the value of LT_1 is obtained by subtracting the duration of A from the value of LT_2 .

1.5.3 Determination of slacks

Once we know the earliest and latest times of occurrence for the nodes, we can determine the earliest and latest start and completion times for the activities. The latest starting time (LST) and the earliest completion time (ECT) of an activity are defined from the expressions:

$$LST_{ij} = LT_j - d_{ij}$$

$$ECT_{ij} = ET_i + d_{ij}$$

The earliest start time (EST) and the latest conclusion time (LCT) of activity X_{ij} coincide with the earliest time (ET) and the latest time (LT) of occurrence of nodes i and j, respectively, between which the activity takes place.

Total float

The total float (or total slack) is the total time that the starting of an activity can be delayed, or the conclusion anticipated, without disturbing the total duration of the project (it is available if the starting of activities on the left is not delayed and on the right is delayed).

An activity without slack is called critical.

As the maximum time available to conclude the activity X_{ij} is LT_j – ET_i, the total float (TF) is defined by subtracting from the maximum available time the duration of the activity:

$$TF_{ij} = LT_j - ET_i - d_{ij}$$

Considering the earliest and the latest times of starting and finishing the activity, the TF can alternatively be determined from the following expressions:

$$TF_{ij} = LST_{ij} - EST_{ij} = LCT_{ij} - ECT_{ij}$$

The following figure illustrates the definition of total slack from these expressions, taking into account the time available to implement the activity and the option to start it as soon as possible or to delay it as long as possible.

Using the total slack of an activity can limit the start and end times of other activities. To avoid affecting the start and end times of other activities, free floats are defined.

The critical path

The total duration of the project is the shortest period in which it can be completed and is determined by a sequence of activities called the critical path.

The activities without slack, i.e., the critical activities, are part of the critical path.

The project's time management focuses on controlling critical activities. Since these activities have no slack, if delayed, they push the project's terminal period.

Free float to the right

The free float to the right (FFR), or simply free float, and also known as tail slack (e.g. [3]), represents the time that the start of an activity can be delayed without conditioning the start of succeeding activities.

To avoid conditioning the start of the activities that follow in node j , we have to keep the possibility of starting them in ET_j . In these conditions, the time available for activity X_{ij} is reduced to $ET_j - ET_i$, and the FFR is evaluated using the expression:

$$FFR_{ij} = ET_j - ET_i - d_{ij}$$

The following figure illustrates graphically the definition of the free float to the right, taking into account the reduction of the time available to implement activity X_{ij} , so as not to condition the start of the activities on the right:

Free float to the left

The free float to the left (FFL), also known as head slack, represents the time that the completion of an activity can be anticipated without conditioning the conclusion of antecedent activities.

To avoid conditioning the completion of predecessor activities, in node i , we must maintain the possibility that they may end in LT_i . In these conditions, the time available for activity X_{ij} is reduced to $LT_j - LT_i$, and the FFL is evaluated using the expression:

$$FFL_{ij} = LT_j - LT_i - d_{ij}$$

The following figure illustrates graphically the definition of the free float to the left, taking into account the reduction of the time available to implement activity X_{ij} , without conditioning the completion of the activities on the left:

Independent float

The independent float (IF) represents the time that the beginning of an activity can be delayed without conditioning the start of the subsequent activities, or the time that the conclusion can be anticipated without conditioning the conclusion of the antecedent activities. In this case, the time available to implement activity X_{ij} is only $ET_j - LT_i$, and the independent float is assessed using the expression:

$$IF_{ij} = ET_j - LT_i - d_{ij}$$

The following figure illustrates graphically the definition of the independent float, taking into account the reduction in the time available to implement activity X_{ij} , without conditioning the beginning of activities on the right and the completion of activities on the left:

Example

The (i, j) network shown in the following figure includes activity durations and presents the earliest and latest times for each node.

The free float to the right of activity D represents the maximum delay allowed for the start of D, in order to allow activity F to start at $t = 11$. Its evaluation involves the times of nodes 2 and 4, as illustrated below:

$$FFR(D) = ET(4) - ET(2) - d(D) = 11 - 3 - 3 = 5$$

That is, instead of starting at $t = 3$, we can delay the start of activity D up to $t = 8$, so that it can end before (or at) $t = 11$.

The free float to the left of activity D represents the maximum anticipation allowed for the completion of D in order to allow activity A to end at $t = 7$. Its evaluation involves the times of nodes 2 and 4, as shown next:

$$\text{FFL(D)} = \text{LT(4)} - \text{LT(2)} - d(\text{D}) = 15 - 7 - 3 = 5$$

That is, activity D can start at $t = 7$ and end at $t = 10$, anticipating its conclusion in 5 time units.

The independent float of activity D represents the slack available to not condition the completion of activity A or the start of activity F. Its evaluation is obtained from:

$$\text{IF(D)} = \text{ET(4)} - \text{LT(2)} - d(\text{D}) = 11 - 7 - 3 = 1$$

So, if activity D starts at $t = 8$, it will end at $t = 11$, and that does not interfere with the beginning of F. If it ends at $t = 10$, it has to start at $t = 7$, and that does not interfere with the conclusion of A.

The total float of activity D represents the maximum slack available if activity A terminates as early as possible, and activity F starts as late as possible. Its evaluation is obtained from:

$$\text{TF(D)} = \text{LT(4)} - \text{ET(2)} - d(\text{D}) = 15 - 3 - 3 = 9$$

1.6 Application Examples

Example 1.6.1

The following table presents information related to a project (adapted from [1]). The activity codes are shown, as well as the precedence relations and the duration of the activities (in days).

Activities	Precedences	Duration
A		2
B	A	3
C	A	8
D	A	12
E	A	4
F	E	4
G	B	4
H	D, F	16

Tasks:

- Build the PERT/CPM network of type (i, j)
- Determine the dates of earliest start and latest completion, the total slack, and identify the critical path.

Solution

a) The PERT/CPM network of type (i, j) is shown below. The network construction process involves four steps. In the first step, we introduce the starting node and activity A, which is the only one with the precedence list empty. In the second step, we introduce node two and activities B, C, D, and E, with activity A as the precedence activity. In the third step, we introduce nodes 3 and 4, and activities F and G, which have precedences E and B, respectively. In the fifth step, we introduce node five and activity H, which has two precedences, D and F. To complete the network, we introduce

node 6, which signals the project completion and marks the convergence of activities C, G, and H.

b) To evaluate the earliest time and the latest time, we start by introducing the durations of the activities into the network, and introduce a box next to each node, for the introduction of the earliest and latest times of the nodes, as shown below.

The earliest times of the nodes

We start by determining the earliest dates for the nodes, which will be placed in the boxes in the left-hand cell.

The earliest dates at each node are determined by assuming that the activities that can start there begin as early as possible.

To determine the earliest starting dates for activities that start in a node, we must first evaluate the earliest completion dates for the activities on the left of that node (i.e., those that end at that node).

If we have more than one activity on the left, for example, as in node 5, we have to choose the maximum completion date (i.e., H can only start when both D and F are completed).

The earliest date calculation begins at node 1, which is assigned a value of 0 (representing the start of time counting). If we start activity A at t = 0, we will finish it

at $t = 2$, which is the earliest date on node 2. Therefore, activities that start on node two can start when the time counter shows $t = 2$.

In node 4, the earliest time is equal to 6, which is obtained by adding the Duration of E to the earliest time in node 2.

In node 3, the earliest time is 5, obtained by adding the Duration of B to the earliest time of 2.

In node 5, we first evaluate the earliest completion dates of F and D, then choose the highest value, which is 14 (D's completion).

In the final node, we evaluate the completion dates for C, G, and H and select the highest value, which is 30 days. This value is the project's duration.

Latest time of nodes

The latest node dates are shown in the cells on the right.

The latest node dates are evaluated assuming we delay the start of activities as much as possible, while respecting the project's duration.

The calculations for the latest dates begin at the last node, and then we go back to the initial node and subtract the activity durations.

The latest dates of the nodes represent the latest time for completing the activities that end at those nodes. To evaluate them, we must first determine the latest starting times of the activities that start at the node.

In the last node, the latest time equals the earliest time, representing the project's duration. So, regarding our example, the latest time in node 6 is 30.

In node 5, for activity H to end in 30, it must start in $30 - 16 = 14$. This is the value of the latest time of node 5. In node 3, it is $30 - 4 = 26$, and in node 4, it is $14 - 4 = 10$.

In node 2, we have the beginning of B, C, D, and E. The latest beginning of B is $26 - 3 = 23$, that of C is $30 - 8 = 22$, that of D is $14 - 12 = 2$, and that of E is $10 - 4 = 6$. Therefore, for the duration of the project to be respected, activity D must start at $t = 2$, and so activity A cannot end after $t = 2$. Hence, the latest time of node 2 equals the minimum of the latest starting times of the activities that start in node 2.

The latest time of node one is obtained by subtracting the Duration of A from the latest time of node 2.

From the earliest and latest times of the nodes, we can associate the earliest and latest times for starting and finishing the activities.

The earliest start time of an activity equals the earliest time at the node where it starts. The latest time for completing an activity is equal to the latest time at the node where the activity ends. The difference between these two times equals the total time available to implement the activity.

Total float (or slack) represents the extra time available to implement the activity. It is obtained by subtracting the activity's duration from the total time available to implement it. The critical path is the path that defines the project's duration and consists of critical activities with zero total float.

In the following table, we present the earliest starting time (EST), the latest completion time (LCT), and the total float (TF).

Activities	Duration	EST	LCT	TF
A	2	0	2	0
B	3	2	26	21
C	8	2	30	20
D	12	2	14	0
E	4	2	10	4
F	4	6	14	4
G	4	5	30	21
H	16	14	30	0

The data in this table indicate that the project's critical activities are A, D, and H. The total duration of these activities is $2 + 12 + 16 = 30$, which equals the project's duration.

In the following network, we identified the critical path using double-dashed arrows.

Example 1.6.2

The following table provides information about the project to build a house. The table shows the activity codes, precedence relations, and activity durations (adapted from [2]). The network (i, j), shown in the following figure, includes information on the duration of the activities and presents the earliest and latest dates for each node.

We will use this example to evaluate the earliest and latest times for starting and terminating the activities, the total float, and to identify the critical path.

Activities	Activity codes	Precedences	Duration (W)
Foundations	A		1
Wall structure	B	A	2
Roof structure	C	B	2
Walls of the ground-floor	D	B	3
Walls of the cover	E	C	3
Coverage	F	C	5
Installation of water and light	G	D, E	3
Frames	H	D, E	2
Interior finishes	I	G, H	8
Exterior finishes	J	H	4
External arrangements	K	F, J	1

To evaluate the activity dates, we built the table shown below using the earliest time (ET) and the latest time (LT) for each node.

The earliest starting time of an activity is equal to the earliest time of the node where it can be started ($EST_{ij} = ET_i$), and the latest completion time of the activity is equal to the latest time of the node where it must end ($LCT_{ij} = LT_j$).

The earliest completion time of an activity is obtained by adding its duration to its earliest starting time ($ECT_{ij} = EST_{ij} + d_{ij}$).

The latest starting time of an activity is obtained by subtracting its duration from its latest completion time ($LST_{ij} = LCT_{ij} - d_{ij}$).

The total slack of an activity can be obtained by subtracting the completion times or the starting times (i.e., $TF = LCT - ECT$ or $TF = LST - EST$).

The critical path consists of activities with total float equal to zero, namely A, B, C, E, G, and I.

The critical path is represented in the PERT/CPM network by double-dashed arrows.

Act.	d	EST	ECT	LST	LCT	TF	C
A	1	0	1	0	1	0	X
B	2	1	3	1	3	0	X
C	2	3	5	3	5	0	X
D	3	3	6	5	8	2	
E	3	5	8	5	8	0	X
F	5	5	10	13	18	8	
G	3	8	11	8	11	0	X
H	2	8	10	9	11	1	
I	8	11	19	11	19	0	X
J	4	10	14	14	18	4	
K	1	14	15	18	19	4	

This table provides all the information the project manager needs to plan the implementation of activities. However, the project manager may prefer to visualize this information in a horizontal bar chart, also known as a Gantt chart.

Gantt charts can be used to visualize the planning and execution of activities, and to show the project's progress over time and cost.

The following figure presents the Gantt chart for planning the execution of this project, assuming all activities begin on their earliest start dates.

In this graph, the time intervals for implementing activities are represented by boxes. The days on which activities will be implemented are represented in a darker color.

The days corresponding to the time slacks are represented in a lighter color. In this case, critical activities are characterized by the absence of time slacks.

1.7 Using Linear Programming⁴

Using PERT/CPM networks of the type (i, j) allowed us to introduce the elementary concepts for scheduling the project's activities. Using this tool, the concepts of activity start and end times, the different types of slacks, and the critical path emerge naturally.

However, these networks are merely graphical representations of the set of activities, subject to the restrictions imposed by the precedence relationships. In fact, it is possible to build a table with all the necessary information, as shown in the previous example, including start and end times, earliest and latest, and total floats, without using any graphical representation.

PERT/CPM networks essentially allow us to solve a linear programming problem manually, but this problem can also be solved numerically without the need to previously know the network or any other form of graphical representation.

Using example 1.6.2 to illustrate the procedure of building the table with the times associated to the activities, shown on the previous page, we first formulate the problem to determine the earliest start times of the activities.

In this case, the decision variables are the earliest starting times (EST). As these times are defined assuming that all activities start as early as possible, the objective is to minimize the sum of these times. The restrictions state that the start of each activity can occur only after its predecessors are completed.

Under these conditions, from the precedence table presented on example 1.6.2, we obtain the following problem, which we present in a format suitable for introduction in Classic LINDO⁵ linear programming (LP)⁶ software:

```

MIN  ESTA + ESTB + ESTC + ESTD + ESTE + ESTF + ESTG +
      ESTH + ESTI + ESTJ + ESTK
S.T.
ESTB - ESTA >= 1
ESTC - ESTB >= 2
ESTD - ESTB >= 2
ESTE - ESTC >= 2
ESTF - ESTC >= 2
ESTG - ESTD >= 3
ESTH - ESTD >= 3
ESTI - ESTG >= 3
ESTJ - ESTH >= 2
ESTK - ESTF >= 5
ESTG - ESTE >= 3
ESTH - ESTE >= 3
ESTI - ESTH >= 2
ESTK - ESTJ >= 4
END

```

⁴ This section can be omitted without loss of continuity!

⁵ Classic LINDO software is available here: <https://www.lindo.com/index.php/ls-downloads>

⁶ If formulating Linear Programming problems is a new subject for you, you can see an introduction to the topic in the following video: [Modeling Problems in LP](#).

We can solve this LP problem using software such as LINDO, LPSOLVE⁷, the Excel Solver, or a programming language such as Python.

The solution we obtained is shown in the following table, together with the earliest completion times, computed by adding the activity durations to the earliest start times.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
EST	0	1	3	3	5	5	8	8	11	10	14
ECT	1	3	5	6	8	10	11	10	19	14	15

From these results, we identified the project duration ($D_p = 19$) as the earliest completion time (it is the highest value of the earliest completion times).

Next, we formulate the problem to evaluate the latest starting times of activities. In this case, the decision variables are the latest starting times (LST), and as these times are defined assuming that all activities start as late as possible, the objective is to maximize the sum of times.

The restrictions state that the start of each activity can occur only after its predecessors are completed. However, we need additional restrictions for activities whose codes are not on the precedence list. In our example, as shown in the following table, we crossed out the activities that appear on both sides; these are activities I and K. For these activities, the latest starting time can be defined immediately by subtracting their durations from the project duration.

Under these conditions, we obtain the following LP problem:

```

MAX LSTA + LSTB + LSTC + LSTD + LSTE + LSTF + LSTG +
    LSTH + LSTI + LSTJ + LSTK
S. T.
LSTB - LSTA >= 1
LSTC - LSTB >= 2
LSTD - LSTB >= 2
LSTE - LSTC >= 2
LSTF - LSTC >= 2
LSTG - LSTD >= 3
LSTH - LSTD >= 3
LSTI - LSTG >= 3
LSTJ - LSTH >= 2
LSTK - LSTF >= 5
LSTG - LSTE >= 3
LSTH - LSTE >= 3
LSTI - LSTH >= 2
LSTK - LSTJ >= 4
LSTI = 11
LSTK = 18
END
    
```

A		
B	A	
C	B	
D	B	
E	C	
F	C	
G	D	E
H	D	E
I	G	H
J	H	
K	F	J

The solution to this problem is presented in the following table, which also includes the solution to the previous problem and the latest time to complete each activity (LCT). From these values, we can also evaluate the total slack of activities (TF) and identify the critical activities with $TF = 0$.

⁷ LPSOLVE software is available here: <https://sourceforge.net/projects/lpsolve/>

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
EST	0	1	3	3	5	5	8	8	11	10	14
ECT	1	3	5	6	8	10	11	10	19	14	15
LST	0	1	3	5	5	13	8	9	11	14	18
LCT	1	3	5	8	8	18	11	11	19	18	19
TF	0	0	0	2	0	8	0	1	0	4	4

Here, we do not use the PERT/CPM network of type (i, j) of example 1.6.2, but we adopt essentially the same steps to obtain this solution.⁸

We first evaluate the earliest possible start times, assuming activities start as soon as possible. Then, from the solution to the first problem, we identify the project's duration and define the second problem imposing that duration. In this case, given that activities are implemented as late as possible, we evaluate the latest possible starting times.

⁸ Depending on the problem we want to solve, we can also construct LP problems based on network knowledge, as illustrated in [3] and in the video: [USING LP IN PERT/CPM NETWORKS](#).

Chapter 2: Uncertainty in Project Management

Chapter Overview

This chapter examines how uncertainty – the lack of knowledge about future events – affects project scheduling and duration estimation. It extends the deterministic PERT/CPM framework introduced in the previous chapter to account for the probabilistic nature of activity duration. It explains how the PERT method incorporates probabilistic activity durations, modeled through the Beta distribution. Using examples, it shows how to estimate the probability of meeting deadlines and how to determine confidence-based completion times.

2.1 Uncertainty regarding the duration of activities

The duration of an activity is not always known precisely. In practice, we estimate the term to which we can associate a probability of materializing. The probabilistic nature of the duration of the activities is considered in the PERT method, proposing that in relation to the duration of each activity, three estimates are made:

i) An optimistic estimate (Dop):

It is an estimate of realization under very favorable conditions. In probabilistic terms, these conditions imply that the probability of completing the activity in a shorter period than Dop is negligible (i.e., less than 1%).

ii) A most likely estimate (Dmp):

This scenario assumes that everything will proceed as usual.

iii) A pessimistic estimate (Dpe):

It is an estimate of realization in very adverse conditions. In this scenario, we assume that the probability of completing the activity in a period longer than Dpe is negligible (i.e., less than 1%).

Intuitively, we know that, in projects of practical interest, it is not possible to reduce the duration of an activity to zero or extend its duration to infinity. What we can do is establish the lower and upper bounds of the duration, and associate probabilities, as we described earlier, which is represented schematically in the following figure:

When we try to model the problem statistically, we face a mathematical difficulty arising from the relative position of the most likely duration (Dmp).

There is no justification for assuming that Dmp will be located in the middle of the range defined by Dpe and Dop. There will be practical situations in which this estimate will be closer to Dop and others in which it will be closer to Dpe.

To address the diversity of Dmp location possibilities, we need a probabilistic distribution of activity duration that can take different forms to accommodate all possibilities.

The analytical distribution used in this area, with the versatility necessary to represent the set of situations that may occur, is the Beta distribution. The probability density function (pdf) of the Beta distribution can be defined using the following expression:

$$pdf_x = \frac{x^{\alpha-1} (1-x)^{\beta-1}}{\int_0^1 x^{\alpha-1} (1-x)^{\beta-1} dx}$$

Where α and β are positive parameters and $0 \leq x \leq 1$.

To apply this model to the duration of an activity, we have to relate the duration D to x . Analytically, it is not easy, but for practical purposes, we know it will not deviate much from the relationship: $D = D_{Op} + x(D_{Pe} - D_{Op})$.

To illustrate the versatility of this distribution in accommodating the diversity of profile shapes related to the duration of an activity, we present in the following figure some examples of the forms the Beta distribution can take.

In that figure, we present four distributions corresponding to 4 parameter sets (α, β) . For example, the situation with $\alpha = 2$ and $\beta = 10$ illustrates the case where D_{mp} is much closer to D_{op} , whereas the situation with $\alpha = 10$ and $\beta = 2$ illustrates the case where D_{mp} is much closer to D_{pe} . On the other hand, the situations considered in which $\alpha = \beta$ show that, even in this case, the Beta distribution can have very different forms: it can either be similar to the Gaussian distribution or it can approximate the uniform distribution.

The Beta distribution is also important for modeling the duration of activities because its statistical parameters (first and second moments) can be estimated from 3 realizations of the random variable.

For example, considering the duration D of an activity as the random variable, it is possible to demonstrate that we can estimate the expected value of the duration and its variance, using the following expressions:

$$\mu = \frac{D_{op} + 4D_{mp} + D_{pe}}{6}$$

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{(D_{pe} - D_{op})^2}{36}$$

2.2 Statistical Properties of the Critical Path

To evaluate the statistical properties of the critical path, we need some elementary statistical concepts, which we recall below. The expected value and the variance of a random variable x can be defined from the following expressions:

$$\mu = E[x] = \bar{x} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x \, pdf_x \, dx$$

$$\sigma^2 = Var[x] = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (x - \bar{x})^2 \, pdf_x \, dx$$

If we introduce a second random variable, y , into the analysis, the problem becomes more complex because we now have to consider the joint probability density function of x and y . In these conditions, we can evaluate the expected values and the variances of the two variables, using expressions similar to the previous ones, but also the covariance between the two variables, using the following expression:

$$Cov(x, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y}) \, pdf_{xy} \, dx \, dy$$

Bearing in mind that we are interested in the properties of the durations of the activities, and the duration of the project, for conclusions we intend to present, we can assume that the variables x and y represent the durations of the activities X and Y of a project, with only these two sequential activities, and that $z = x + y$ represents the duration of the project. For these conditions, it is easy to verify that we would obtain the following relationships:

$$E[z] = E[x] + E[y]$$

$$Var[z] = Var[x] + Var[y] + 2Cov(x, y)$$

The expression to evaluate the expected value allows us to conclude that the expected value of the duration of the project is equal to the sum of the expected value of the duration of each activity.

Regarding project duration variance, the situation is more complicated, especially when there are more than two activities.

In the situation we are analyzing, the expression of the variance of z , via the covariance term, captures the idea that unexpected changes (positive or negative) in one activity influence the other.

Intuitively, we know that if something goes wrong today, it can negatively influence tomorrow, but its effect is not easy to account for. Consequently, in practice, we assume that activities are independent and that what happens in one activity does not necessarily affect what happens in the others. In this case, the covariance term is null.

Now, to analyze the situation of a project with several activities, in this course and in general, we consider that the critical path defines the project's statistical properties.

Thus, if the project consists of n critical activities to be carried out sequentially, the expected value of the project duration and the value of the variance of the project duration can be evaluated from the expressions:

$$\mu_p = \mu_{C1} + \mu_{C2} + \dots + \mu_{Cn}$$

$$\sigma_p^2 = \sigma_{C1}^2 + \sigma_{C2}^2 + \dots + \sigma_{Cn}^2$$

However, if the number of activities on the critical path is high, we can resort to the Central Limit Theorem, which states that, by aggregating the distributions of individual activities, the distribution of the project's duration tends towards a Gaussian distribution. Therefore, given this possibility, we assume the project duration follows a Gaussian distribution.

To identify the questions that can be asked of the decision maker, when we introduce the uncertainty of the duration of the activities into the problem, let us consider the following example.

Example⁹

The following table presents the duration of a project's activities (in days). The project's PERT/CPM network is also shown in the following figure. We want to determine the following:

- a) The expected duration of the project
- b) The probability of terminating the project in less than 95 days
- c) The deadline for carrying out the project can be met with a 99% probability

Act.	Prec.	Dop	Dmp	Dpe	μ	σ^2
A		25	28	43	30	9.00
B		38	52	54	50	7.11
C		35	40	45	40	2.78
D	A	32	40	48	40	7.11
E	A	24	29	40	30	7.11
F	B, D	17	19	27	20	2.78
G	C	35	40	75	45	44.44

In this table, the values of μ and σ were determined using the expressions previously presented on section 2.1.

In the network shown below, we include details on the calculation of the earliest and latest times for each node, and we identify the critical path with double-dashed arrows.

⁹ Adapted from [2]

It is important to note that the network has to be built using the expected values of the durations, and not the most likely values. We are interested in evaluating the expected value of the duration of the project, which, as we saw earlier, is equal to the sum of the expected values of the critical activities.

a) The expected value and the variance of the project duration are assessed based on the properties of the critical activities (A, D, and F). These properties, that is, the values of μ and σ^2 , were evaluated in the previous table. Taking into account the available information, we obtain the following parameters:

$$\mu_P = \mu_A + \mu_D + \mu_F = 30 + 40 + 20 = 90 \text{ days}$$

$$\sigma_P^2 = \sigma_A^2 + \sigma_D^2 + \sigma_F^2 = 9.0 + 7.11 + 2.78 = 18.89 \text{ days}^2$$

b) To assess the probability of completing the project in less than 95 days, we will assume that the duration of the project is a random variable with a Gaussian distribution, with an expected value of $\mu = 90$ days, and the standard deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{18.89} = 4.35 \text{ of days.}$$

We can use this information to consult a table of the Gaussian distribution and determine the probability value by direct reading. However, in general, we only have the standard (or standardized) Gaussian distribution available, which we can use after the following variable transformation:

$$z = \frac{d - \mu}{\sigma} = \frac{95 - 90}{4.35} = 1.15$$

The standard normal distribution table¹⁰ (Gaussian distribution of Z with zero expected value and unit variance) is often presented for positive z values, and for $P(Z \leq z)$.

Therefore, in our case, we have to assess the probability $P(D_p \leq 95)$, i.e., to evaluate $P(Z \leq 1.15)$. To illustrate how to extract this probability from the Z distribution table, we present the part of the table relevant to this issue in the following figure.

z	0	...	0.04	0.05	0.06
0	0.500		0.516	0.520	0.524
...					
1	0.841		0.851	0.853	0.855
1.1	0.864		0.873	0.875	0.877
1.2	0.885		0.893	0.894	0.896

In the left-hand column, we select the line with the desired z value to the desired decimal precision. In the upper row, we select the column corresponding to the centesimal precision of the z value. At the intersection of the row and column that we record, we read the desired probability value. Therefore, the answer to the question posed is as follows:

$$P(D_p \leq 95) = P(Z \leq 1.15) = 87.5\%$$

¹⁰ The cumulative normal distribution can be evaluated using Excel's NORMDIST function.

In the following figure, we illustrate that the probability we evaluated equals the area under the probability density function for z values less than 1.15.

c) The deadline L for carrying out the project that can be met with a 99% probability is defined using the following expressions:

$$P(D_p \leq L) = 0.99 \Leftrightarrow P\left(Z \leq \frac{L-90}{4.35}\right) = 0.99$$

To answer this question, we consult the standard distribution table to find the probability value closest to 0.99 and directly extract the z value of Z corresponding to the specified probability, as illustrated in the following figure:

z	0.00	...	0.03
0.0	0.500		0.512
⋮			↑
2.3	0.989	←	0.990

From this figure, we conclude that $P(Z \leq 2.33) = 0.99$, and we establish the following relationship, from which we extract the value of L :

$$z = \frac{L-90}{4.35} = 2.33 \rightarrow L = 90 + 2.33 \times 4.35 = 100.13 \text{ days}$$

In other words, to guarantee a period during which the project will be completed with 99% probability, this period is 101 days, since the calculations indicate it is greater than 100 days.

Chapter3: Management of Physical Resources

Chapter Overview

This chapter discusses how to manage and allocate physical resources throughout a project. It distinguishes between cumulative and non-cumulative resources and introduces practical methods to balance their availability and use over time. Through practical examples, it demonstrates how resource-loading maps and occupancy rates can be used to evaluate efficiency, minimize idle time, and adjust project duration when resource constraints exist. This makes the techniques directly applicable to real projects, providing the confidence to manage resources effectively.

3.1 Activity schedule

The implementation of any activity always involves dedicating resources (human and material) to its development. The allocation of these resources always entails a cost, reflecting the deprivation of their use for other purposes.

In the study of project management, it is important to distinguish between resources that can be accumulated and those that cannot.

Cumulative resources (e.g., money, materials, and space) remain available if not used. They allow the establishment of stock, which can be provided according to project needs. It is important to ensure that the accumulated stock of resources is greater than or equal to the accumulated needs (e.g., Inventory Management).

Non-accumulating resources (such as machine hours and person-hours) must be replenished continuously. If not used in the current period, they do not remain available for use in the next one. The analysis to develop these resources should be based on comparisons between use and instant availability.

According to [2], the allocation of the non-accumulating resources available can be seen in the context of two distinct problems, which can be solved using the same approach:

- i) Once the total duration of the project is fixed, it is important to determine the minimum level of each available resource.
- ii) Once the availability of each resource has been fixed over time, it is important to assess the minimum possible project duration.

To illustrate these two approaches, we will use the study examples presented next.

3.2 Application Examples

Example 3.2.1¹¹

The network shown below represents the sequence of activities for a project. In this network, the earliest and latest dates of occurrence of the events are identified. The critical path is identified, with critical activities represented by double-dashed arrows, and the total floats of the sub-critical activities are also shown.

Based on the nodes' times, the planned project duration is 8 days, provided the necessary resources are available to implement the activities.

¹¹ Adapted from [1]

Information on the resources needed to implement the activities is presented in the following table, which also includes additional information taken from the network. The earliest starting times (EST) and the latest conclusion times (LCT), for each activity, are shown, as well as the total float (TF).

The required non-cumulative resources are called resource units (RUs). To simplify our analysis, let us assume each RU represents a technician. For example, when we allocate one RU to activity A, we are saying that it requires the exclusive and permanent dedication of a technician throughout its duration.

Act.	d	EST	LCT	TF	RU
A	4	0	4	0	1
B	3	0	7	4	1
C	5	0	8	3	1
D	4	4	8	0	1
E	1	3	8	4	2

As we mentioned earlier, we may need to address the management of non-cumulative resources using two approaches.

Starting with the most straightforward approach, let us assume the project duration is fixed. In this case, we need to evaluate the number of resource units (NRU) to be dedicated to the project.

To answer this question, we need to build a table, as shown below, called the resource loading map. The resource-loading map is constructed from the information we retrieve from the PERT/CPM network. At the top of the graph, we identify the time, and then we present a line for each activity, with the time allocated to its implementation represented by colored cells.

Resources are loaded by filling the cells reserved for implementing activities with the necessary resource units.

t	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
A	1	1	1	1				
B	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	
C	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-
D					1	1	1	1
E				2	-	-	-	-
RUn	3	3	3	4	2	1	1	1

Map of Resource Loading

For example, activity A is critical, lasts 4 days, and requires 1 RU to be implemented. Based on the information extracted from the network, this activity starts immediately and should therefore be completed within 4 days. On each day of its implementation, it requires one technician (1 RU), so all the colored cells in A are filled with 1 unit.

Regarding activity B, it can be started immediately, but must be finished after 7 days. Since there are no resource limitations, it is good practice to start activities as early as possible. If something unforeseen arises, the gap provides a margin for possible corrections. As activity B lasts 3 days and requires the permanent dedication of a technician, we fill the first three cells reserved for this activity with 1 unit each.

After loading the remaining activities, we add the necessary resources for each activity each day and obtain the project (RUn) resources, which we present in the last line of the table for each day. In this way, we concluded that four technicians (NRU = 4) are needed to implement the project with the presented schedule.

Based on the information from the line RUn, we can also build a diagram of loads, such as the one below, which illustrates the evolution of resource needs for each day.

Diagram of Loads

The diagram of loads is presented in two colors, below and above the load line, to indicate that the area below the load line is proportional to the time used, and the area above the load line is proportional to the time wasted.

To quantify the relationship between the time available and the time used, we define the occupation rate of the resources, using the following expression:

$$\alpha = \frac{RUu}{RUa}$$

Where RUu stands for the resources used (it is proportional to the time used) and RUa represents the resources available (it is proportional to the time available).

In our example, the available resources are $RUa = NRU \times Dp = 4 \times 8 = 32$ units (4 technicians during 8 days). Moreover, the resources used are $RUu = 3 \times 3 + 1 \times 4 + 1 \times 2 + 3 \times 1 = 18$ (area below the load curve). So, the occupation rate is:

$$\alpha = \frac{18}{32} = 0.5625 \quad (\approx 56\%)$$

That is, if the technicians are exclusively dedicated to this project, they are, on average, 44% of their time unoccupied.

In practice, this situation may not occur because technicians can also work on other projects and are assigned to each project only when necessary.

The situation in which the technicians are exclusively dedicated to the project may also happen. However, in this situation, it may be preferable to reduce the number of technicians allocated to the project and increase its duration.

Now, for the second approach, let us assume we have only two technicians available to implement the project (NRU = 2). In this case, we need to identify an alternative schedule for the project's implementation.

To address this issue, we present below a simplified version of the resource loading map. In this version, the activities are represented by arrows of length proportional to their duration and are presented in levels corresponding to the different paths of the PERT/CPM network.

The activities are identified by their codes, which include information on their precedence on the left.

The loading of resources is shown above the arrows, for each activity, and the resource needs are shown below, at different time intervals.

The analysis of resource needs allows us to identify the time intervals during which they exceed the two available units.

In this way, we conclude that, to reduce the load on those days, we need to move some overlapping activities to other time slots.

As activity E requires 2 RU, it must be implemented after the critical activities A and D. It can be implemented after B. However, it does not need to be implemented right after B. On the other hand, by moving B to after the eighth day, we create space to implement C after B (we can also choose to implement B after C).

The resource-loading map resulting from this modification is shown in the figure below. We can see that the project duration increases to 9 days, and in this case, the technicians' occupancy rate is 100%.

This map assumes that activities are implemented in a different order than initially planned, provided that the initial technical conditions are not violated.

The precedences that must be respected in the new programming are those presented in the following table.

Act	A	B	C	D	E
Prec	-	-	B	A	D, C

The initial precedence of D remains, activity C stays with precedence B, and activity E stays with C and D, respecting the condition of being implemented after B.

Example 3.2.2

The following table presents information related to a project. Codes for the activities are shown along with the precedence relations, the activity durations (in days), and the units of resources required per unit of time¹².

Activ.	Prec.	d	RU
A	-	4	2
B	-	3	1
C	-	1	1
D	A	2	1
E	B, C	5	2
F	D, E	3	2
G	F	2	1
H	F	3	1

Tasks:

- a) Build the PERT/CPM network of type (i, j).
- b) For each activity, determine the dates of initiation and conclusion, closer and more remote, the total slack, and identify the critical path.
- c) Build a loading resource map, considering that there are no resource constraints, and evaluate the occupancy rate.
- d) Build a loading resource map, considering that there are only three resource units available per unit of time.

Solution

a) The PERT/CPM of type (i, j) is presented next:

To build the network, we need to follow the steps illustrated in the table, marked in different colors. In the first step, highlighted in the first column in blue, we introduce node 1, which marks the beginning of the project and the activities A, B, and C.

In the second step, indicated in the first column in red, we introduce first node 2 and then activity D. Next, we introduce nodes 3 and 4 to mark the completion of C and B. We introduce E at node four and the fictitious activity of identity between nodes 3 and 4 to indicate that E also has C as a precedent.

¹² Adapted from [1]

In the third step, indicated in the first column in green, we introduce node 5 to signal the completion of activities D and E and start activity F.

In the fourth step, we introduce node 6 to signal the completion of activity F and start activities G and H.

To complete the network, we introduce nodes 7 and 8 to signal the completion of G and H. To close the network, we introduce a fictitious activity of identity between nodes 7 and 8.

b) In order to identify the critical path, we must assess first the earliest and the latest times of the nodes. The following network shows the values of the earliest times in green and the values of the latest times in red:

The calculations start at node one by determining the earliest times. The latest times are evaluated next, starting with node eight and working back to node 1.

After assessing the node times, we must identify the critical path.

The critical path passes through critical nodes (nodes with equal times) and includes only critical activities. Therefore, in this network, the only possible path is 1-4-5-6-8, which includes activities B, E, F, and H.

In the next representation of the network, we identify the critical path with double-dashed arrows and present the total floats of the sub-critical activities in curly brackets, along with their durations.

To determine the start and end dates (earliest and latest) and the total floats for the activities, we can build a table as shown next.

We start by defining the earliest start dates (EST) and the latest conclusion dates (LCT) of the activities, which coincide with the earliest times of the nodes they start and the latest times at the nodes they end, respectively. These dates are taken from the network and are shown in the table with the same colors as in the network.

From these values, we calculate the earliest completion dates ($ECT = EST + d$) and the latest start dates ($LST = LCT - d$), adding and subtracting the duration of the activities, respectively.

The total floats (TF) can be assessed by subtracting the completion times ($LCT - ECT$) or the starting times ($LST - EST$).

Activ.	d	EST	ECT	LST	LCT	TF
A	4	0	4	2	6	2
B	3	0	3	0	3	0
C	1	0	1	2	3	2
D	2	4	6	6	8	2
E	5	3	8	3	8	0
F	3	8	11	8	11	0
G	2	11	13	12	14	1
H	3	11	14	11	14	0

c) To assess the occupancy rate, we have to determine the number of resource units (NRU) needed to implement the project. If there are no resource constraints, we build a resource-loading map, assuming that all activities start as early as possible.

In the following figure, we present a simplified version of the resource-loading map, where the lengths of the arrows is proportional to the duration of the activities. We present the levels corresponding to the different paths of the PERT/CPM network.

Adding the values of each day (i.e., in each column) of the resources needed to implement the activities in progress, we conclude, as shown in the last line of the map, that four resource units are needed ($NRU = 4$).

To assess the occupancy rate, we assess first the available resources RU_a , and the resources used RU_u , as shown below:

$$RU_a = NR_u \times T = 4 \times 14 = 56 \text{ un}$$

$$RU_u = 4 \times 2 + 3 \times 4 + 2 \times 7 + 1 = 35 \text{ un}$$

Under these conditions, the occupancy rate α is given by:

$$\alpha = \frac{35}{56} = 0.625 \quad (62.5\%)$$

d) If only three resource units are available, per unit of time, we have to analyze the previous map and move the activities responsible for overlapping resources over 3. This happens with A, B, and C, and with A and E as well.

Since it is not possible to eliminate the overlap between D and E by moving D, and since E is critical, we have to shift E to start at $t = 4$ instead of $t = 3$ to avoid the intersection of A and E. In this case, C, which has precedence over activity E and only needs 1 RU, can be implemented in the released space. Considering these changes, the resource loading map looks like the following:

In these conditions, the project duration is now 15 days, and the resource occupancy rate has risen to 77.8%.

Chapter 4: Earned Value Management

Chapter Overview

This chapter introduces the Earned Value Management (EVM) methodology, an integrated approach that combines cost, schedule, and performance control. It explains how to measure project progress using the relationships among planned value, earned value, and actual cost. Using practical examples, it shows how to assess schedule and cost variances, calculate performance indexes, and forecast the final project budget under optimistic and pessimistic scenarios.

4.1 The Earned Value Methodology

In Project Management, it is common to use only two cost measures – planned and realized – which may be insufficient.

In the EVM (Earned Value Management) methodology, a distinction is made between the amount spent and the value created. EVM is an integrated planning and control tool that combines cost and time, with progress measured by accumulated person-hours (or added value) and elapsed time.

The application of EVM consists of evaluating, at specific points in time, the cost accomplished and the value of the work performed. These parameters are then compared with the budgeted values for those points in time.

To apply this methodology, three fundamental variables are defined, related to the costs necessary to implement the project:

- BCWS (Budget Cost of Work Scheduled) – it represents the budgeted value of the planned work (or planned value) up to the time considered.
- ACWP (Actual Cost of Work Performed) – this is the real cost of the work done.
- BCWP (Budget Cost of Work Performed) – this is the budgeted amount of work done. Represents the value actually added to the project (Earned Value).

Based on these parameters, we define additional variables to determine whether the project is late or ahead of the initial schedule, and whether it is consuming more or less financial resources than initially planned.

The importance of this approach lies in the problems that arise when expenditure-related and time-related progress, are reported separately. To illustrate the difficulties that may arise, we consider the following example (adapted from [4]). To that end, we present the planned evolution of the accumulated costs in the following figure for a project with duration of 10 days. Considering that 5 days have passed, we also record the evolution of costs actually incurred. We assume here an ideal situation in which costs evolve smoothly and continuously over time.

Comparing only these two curves (planned evolution vs. actual evolution), we could conclude that the project is spending less than expected, with planned expenses at 50% and actual expenses at 45%. Based on this conclusion, we could predict that the project would be completed within the budget.

The following figure adds information about the progress of the work required to implement the activities. In this figure, we also compare the planned progress with the progress made.

In this case, the comparison is not very good because the planned progress was 50% of the total work, while the progress made was only 40%.

When the two graphics are integrated, we conclude that the project spent 45% of the budget but completed only 40% of the work.

The analysis now indicates that not only is the project delayed, but it is also spending more than initially planned.

4.2 Calculations and Terminology

The application of the EVM methodology consists of evaluating, at specific points in time, the cost and value of the work performed. These parameters are then compared with the budgeted values for those periods (e.g. [4]). The process involves three phases:

- Earned Value Planning: assessment of the project budget and cost planning over time.
- Earned Value Status: assessment of progress and costs at specific points in time.
- Earned Value Forecast: review of the project budget.

4.2.1 Earned Value Planning

This phase is carried out before the project starts, and consists of drawing up the project budget and assessing the temporal evolution of the accumulated costs.

The budget amount is represented by the variable BAC (Budget At Completion), and the time evolution of the costs accumulated is described by the variable BCWS (Budget Cost of Work Scheduled).

To illustrate the application of EVM, we consider a situation in which the expected project duration is T , the BAC is 2000 €, and a single point in time, T_n , is used to assess progress.

Up to T_n , BCWS costs of € 1000 are expected, covering the costs necessary to implement three activities: A, B, and C, with estimated costs of 400, 400, and 200 Euros, respectively.

4.2.2 Earned Value Status

Once the project has started, progress needs to be captured regularly. For this purpose, T_n (Time now) instants are defined, indicating the date until which the progress was recorded. At each T_n , information on costs and work performed is obtained, which is used to define two essential variables, BCWP and ACWP, the meaning of which is presented below:

- BCWP (Budget Cost of Work Performed) – it is a measure of the value of the work done up to T_n (represents the "Earned Value", that is, the amount of work actually done, measured em budget units)
- ACWP (Actual Cost of Work Performed) – it represents the effective cost of the work performed up to T_n .

Based on the example we illustrated in the previous phase, we present in the following table the data that is supposedly obtained regarding the project's actual progress.

In this table, we first present the budgeted amount of work expected to be carried out through T_n , and then the percentage PC (Percentage Complete) of the estimated work actually completed. We can see, for example, that the planned work for A and B has been fully completed, but that the work for C has not been implemented.

Based on the PC value of each activity, we calculate the budgeted value of the work actually carried out (BCWP). For example, since the work for activity A was 100% complete, the budgeted amount of work done in A is 400€. On the other hand, as in C, we were unable to do any work, so the budgeted amount of work done in C is zero.

Another important piece of information, which was supposedly collected on the ground, is the amount actually paid for the work performed, which we record in the variable ACWP (Actual Cost of Work Performed). For example, work related to A was budgeted at 400 €, but ended up costing 600 €.

T _n	BCWS	PC (%)	BCWP	ACWP
A	400	100	400	600
B	400	100	400	600
C	200	0	0	0
	1000		800	1200

Based on this information, and considering the budgeted value of the project (BAC), we can assess the percentage of project work already done (PC):

$$PC = \frac{BCWP}{BAC} = \frac{800}{2000} = 0.4$$

Given that it was planned to carry out up to 50% of the total work (BCWS/BAC = 0.5), the project is delayed because we completed only 40%.

The information presented in the previous table can also be used to build a graph, as shown below.

Compared to the graph from the previous phase, with the information now available, we can define two new curves: one for ACWP and one for BCWP.

The BCWP curve is an indicator of the progress of the work being carried out. However, as in this case, where it lies below the initial BCWS curve, we can predict that the project will be delayed and take longer than initially planned.

The ACWP curve shows the evolution of project costs, and because it is above the initial BCWS, we can predict that the project will be more expensive than initially estimated.

To quantify these conclusions, we define variances and performance indexes, which we present next.

Schedule Variance

The Schedule Variance (SV) is a measure of the time deviation, quantified in monetary units. It is evaluated through the difference between the budgeted values of the work performed and the planned work:

$$SV = BCWP - BCWS$$

Taking into account the data of the study example, we obtain:

$$SV = 800 - 1000 = -200 \text{ €}$$

In other words, the work cost accumulated is less 200€ than initially planned. As the work performed is less than planned, we conclude that the project is delayed.

The SV value can also be presented in relative terms, as shown below:

$$SV\% = \frac{SV}{BCWS} = \frac{-200}{1000} = -20\%$$

In this case, we say that the project completed less than 20% of the planned work.

We can also define the Schedule Performance Index (SPI), as shown below:

$$SPI = \frac{BCWP}{BCWS} = \frac{800}{1000} = 80\%$$

In other words, the project carried out only 80% of the planned work.

The following figure illustrates the definition of the Schedule Variance and shows the extrapolation of the BCWP curve, which indicates that the project will end later.

Cost Variance

The Cost Variance (CV) is a measure of the accumulated value of actual expenses, relative to the budget of the work performed. It is evaluated through the difference of the values of the work done, i.e., budgeted and actual:

$$CV = BCWP - ACWP$$

Taking into account the data of the study example, we obtain:

$$CV = 800 - 1200 = -400 \text{ €}$$

In other words, the project accumulated a value of less 400€. As the work carried out exceeded the budget, we conclude that the project will be more expensive than anticipated.

The CV value can also be presented in relative terms, as shown below:

$$CV\% = \frac{CV}{BCWP} = \frac{-400}{800} = -50\%$$

In this case, we say that the amount wasted is 50% of the accumulated value.

We can also define the Cost Performance Index (CPI), as shown below:

$$CPI = \frac{BCWP}{ACWP} = \frac{800}{1200} = 66.67\%$$

In other words, the project accumulated only 2/3 of the funds used.

The following figure illustrates the definition of cost variance and shows the extrapolation of the ACWP curve, which indicates that the project's cost will exceed the initially estimated value.

4.2.3 Earned Value Forecast

Based on the results of the previous phase, we can estimate the actual costs of the project. To do this, we define two new variables, EAC and ETC, whose meanings are presented below:

- EAC (Estimate At Completion) – it represents the revised value of the total project budget based on the ACWP value.
- ETC (Estimate To Complete) – it is an estimate of the cost of work that remains to be done.

These variables are related through the expression:

$$EAC = ETC + ACWP$$

To estimate the EAC and ETC values, we consider two opposing scenarios. One in which we assume that current productivity prevails (for example, when we are unable to correct any problems) and another in which we assume that from now on, everything will go as planned initially (e.g., we can eliminate the detected problems).

Considering these two scenarios yields two forecasts for the project's total budget – one optimistic and one pessimistic – and it is reasonable to assume the final budget will fall within these estimates.

The reference values used for these estimates are illustrated graphically in the following figure:

i) Current productivity prevails

In this case, the discrepancy between BCWP and ACWP will remain until the end of the project. Consequently, the initial value of the budget (BAC) and the value of the EAC forecast also reflect this discrepancy, which leads us to the following relationship:

$$\frac{BCWP}{ACWP} = \frac{BAC}{EAC}$$

Particularizing for the study example, we obtain:

$$EAC = BAC \frac{ACWP}{BCWP} = 2000 \frac{1200}{800} = 3000 \text{ €}$$

From this value and the ACWP value, we obtain the ETC value:

$$\begin{aligned} ETC &= EAC - ACWP \\ &= 3000 - 1200 = 1800 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

ii) Remaining work performed as originally planned

If the problems are eliminated, it is reasonable to assume that there will be no unnecessary costs. In this case, the costs to complete the remaining work are equal to the budgeted amount. In these conditions, we can determine ETC from the original budget amount (BAC) and the budgeted amount of the work performed (BCWP):

$$\begin{aligned} ETC &= BAC - BCWP \\ &= 2000 - 800 = 1200 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

From this value and the value of the real cost of the work already done, we obtain the estimate of the total budget for this scenario:

$$\begin{aligned} EAC &= ETC + ACWP \\ &= 1200 + 1200 = 2400 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

4.3 Applying the Earned Value Methodology

The notes below aim to apply EVM methodology knowledge to a simple case study. However, despite its simplicity, it illustrates the steps involved in defining the information and evaluating the results that allow conclusions to be drawn about the project's evolution.

The study example we will use is a project with three activities, whose PERT/CPM network is shown below. In the network, we also present the activity durations, the earliest and latest times of the nodes, and identify the critical path.

Using information from the network, we can build the following table that identifies the duration of activities and the time intervals in which they can be implemented, along with the earliest and latest times at which the activities start and end, respectively.

In this table, we also present information about the non-cumulative resources needed to implement each activity. To facilitate the presentation of the case, we can assume that each resource unit (RU) required corresponds to a technician. The table also shows that, in this project, each activity requires a technician's permanent dedication.

	d	EST	LCT	RU
A	4	0	6	1
B	6	4	12	1
C	12	0	12	1

In this example, we assume that the direct costs of the project are limited to the costs related to the resource units. We also assume that each resource unit has an operating cost (CRu) of €100 per day per unit.

Building the Earned Value Plan

The necessary planning to implement the EVM methodology begins with evaluating the project budget. The project budget is the budget needed to implement all activities.

Starting, for example, with activity A, the budget cost (BC) is assessed by multiplying the duration (d) by the number of resource units needed (RU) and the unit cost of the resource unit (CRu), as shown below:

$$BC(A) = d \times RU \times CRu = 4 \times 1 \times 100 = 400 \text{ €}$$

Similarly, we obtain for activities B and C:

$$BC(B) = 6 \times 100 = 600 \text{ €}$$

$$BC(C) = 12 \times 100 = 1200 \text{ €}$$

Adding these costs, we obtain the project budget (BAC):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{BAC} &= \text{BC(A)} + \text{BC(B)} + \text{BC(C)} \\ &= 400 + 600 + 1200 = 2200 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

Next, we need to build the budget evolution over time, which we represent as BCWS (Budget Cost of Work Scheduled). For that, we need to build a cost-loading map, as shown below. To build this map, we decided to use 2-day intervals and evaluate the required financial resources for each 2 days. To facilitate this process, we first built the table below:

	d	EST	LCT	BC (€/2d)
A	4	0	6	200
B	6	4	12	200
C	12	0	12	200

In this table, we retrieve the information we previously presented and add the necessary costs for 2 days for each activity.

Thus, to build the following map, we start by drawing the boxes that define the time intervals for implementing each activity. Next, we shade the interval corresponding to each activity's duration (in this example, we highlight the cells in yellow), assuming it is implemented as soon as possible. Finally, we introduce the necessary financial resources over the shaded cells.

Using this map, we evaluate the financial resources required for each 2-day (BC) period. Next, we obtain the accumulated costs over time (BCWS). That is, we start with $\text{BCWS} = \text{BC}$, and at each next instant t , we add the value of BC of instant t to the previous value of BCWS. As expected, the final value of BCWS equals the value of BAC.

In this phase, we also define the points in time T_n (Time now) at which we will check progress after the project starts. For this example, we set $T_n = 6$ days.

t	0	2	4	6	8	10	12
A		200	200				
B				200	200	200	
C		200	200	200	200	200	200
BC		400	400	400	400	400	200
BCWS		400	800	1200	1600	2000	2200

$T_n = 6$ $T = 12$

The Earned Value Status at T_n

To characterize the project's progress up to T_n , we need to collect information about what actually happened. The necessary information is the amount of work actually done in each activity and the actual costs incurred with that work.

Starting with the work already carried out, the following map shows the part completed for each activity (orange) and the remaining part (yellow).

Of course, this data is only assumed to simulate what could have actually happened if T_n days had already passed since the start of the project.

In the following table, we present this information, quantifying the percentage of work completed up to T_n , as well as the costs actually incurred and recorded.

The actual costs of each activity are defined by the variable ACWS (Actual Cost of Work Performed). The percentage of work performed (PC) for each activity is defined as the time spent on the activity divided by its planned duration.

	PC	ACWP (€)
A	4/4 (100%)	300
B	3/6 (50%)	400
C	3/12 (25%)	400
		1100

The actual cost information, up to T_n , must be compared with the budgeted costs for the work that was actually implemented. For this, we evaluated the variable BCWP (Budget Cost of Work Performed), which we present in the following table:

	BC (€)	PC	BCWP (€)
A	400	1	400
B	600	0.5	300
C	1200	0.25	300
			1000

Comparing BCWP to ACWP, we can conclude that we spent more than planned on the work done.

To determine whether the project is delayed, we evaluate the BCWS (Budget Cost of Work Scheduled), which represents the planned progress in work implementation, assuming that 100% of the work corresponds to BAC.

The value of BCWS can be taken directly from the cost loading map we presented earlier, or it can be calculated by multiplying the budgeted cost of each activity by the percentage of work scheduled up to T_n . These calculations are shown in the following table:

	BC (€)	PCs	BCWS (€)
A	400	1	400
B	600	0.333	200
C	1200	0.5	600
			1200

Given the BAC value, the percentage of work actually performed is lower than the percentage scheduled. Thus, we can say that the project is delayed:

$$PC = \frac{BCWP}{BAC} = \frac{1000}{2200} = 45.4\%$$

$$PCs = \frac{BCWS}{BAC} = \frac{1200}{2200} = 54.5\%$$

Therefore, by comparing only the values of ACWP, BCWP, and BCWS, we can assess the evolution of costs and the progress of the project's work. To quantify these conclusions, we use the variances and indices that we analyze below.

Schedule Variance

The Schedule Variance (SV) is used to identify variations in the project's completion period. This parameter is evaluated from the budgeted costs. It compares the budgeted costs of the work performed with those of the planned work.

As the work is measured in monetary units, with reference to BAC, BCWP represents the value earned (or accumulated) by the project from the work done.

As in our example, because BCWP is lower than BCWS, we get a negative SV, indicating that the project has accumulated less value than planned and is therefore delayed.

The same conclusion can be reached using other indicators such as SV% and SPI (Schedule Performance Index), which are presented below.

$$\begin{aligned}SV &= BCWP - BCWS \quad (\text{Achieved} - \text{Planned}) \\ &= 1000 - 1200 = -200 \text{ €} \\ SV\% &= \frac{SV}{BCWS} = -\frac{200}{1200} = -16.67\% \\ SPI &= \frac{BCWP}{BCWS} = \frac{1000}{1200} = 0.833\end{aligned}$$

The conclusions that we can draw from the previous results are as follows:

- The work performed accumulated -200 € of value (BC) than planned.
- The accumulated value is 16.67% lower than planned.
- The accumulated value is only 83.3% of the planned value.

Cost Variance

The cost variance is used to identify deviations in the project budget. This parameter is evaluated by comparing the budgeted costs for the work performed (BCWP) and the costs actually paid (ACWP).

Since BCWP represents the accumulated value from the work performed and ACWP represents the value used to perform the work, a negative CV indicates a waste of value. Therefore, based on the results from our example data, the project will require a higher budget.

$$\begin{aligned}CV &= BCWP - ACWP \quad (\text{Created} - \text{Used}) \\ &= 1000 - 1100 = -100 \text{ €}\end{aligned}$$

The same conclusion can be reached using other indicators, such as CV% and CPI, presented below.

$$CV\% = \frac{CV}{BCWP} = -\frac{100}{1000} = -10\%$$

$$\text{CPI} = \frac{\text{BCWP}}{\text{ACWP}} = \frac{1000}{1100} = 0.91$$

The conclusions that we can draw from the previous results are as follows:

- The work performed created less than 100€ of value than the actual value used.
- The loss of value is 10% of the created value.
- The value created is 91% of the value used.

The Earned Value Forecast at T_n

If cost deviations are detected during the status phase, we can forecast the project budget. In this case, the revised budget is represented by the variable EAC (Estimate at Completion), and the budget required to complete the remaining work is represented by ETC (Estimate to Complete). These two values are related through ACWP, as shown below:

$$\text{EAC} = \text{ETC} + \text{ACWP}$$

To make the predictions, two scenarios are considered: a pessimistic one, in which the problems that caused the observed deviations are assumed to be irreparable, and an optimistic one, in which the opposite is assumed.

i) Current productivity prevailing

In this case, an observed relative discrepancy between ACWP and BCWP will remain until the end. Then, we can establish the following relationship, which relates the discrepancy observed in T_n to the one that will prevail in the future, between EAC and BAC:

$$\frac{\text{BCWP}}{\text{ACWP}} = \frac{\text{BAC}}{\text{EAC}}$$

In this way, using the data in the example, we obtain the values of EAC and ETC using the following expressions:

$$\text{EAC} = \text{BAC} \frac{\text{ACWP}}{\text{BCWP}} = 2200 \frac{1100}{1000} = 2420 \text{ €}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ETC} &= \text{EAC} - \text{ACWP} \\ &= 2420 - 1100 = 1320 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

ii) Remaining work performed as planned

In this case, we assume that the observed discrepancies will be eliminated. Under these conditions, the remaining work will be carried out as initially planned. The total work of the project is the BAC, and the work already completed is the BCWP. Therefore, based on these variables, we conclude that the remaining work corresponds to BAC – BCWP. If this work is performed without deviations, the ETC costs of the future work are BAC – BCWP. Therefore, using the data in the example, we obtain the value of ETC first and then EAC, using the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ETC} &= \text{BAC} - \text{BCWP} \\ &= 2200 - 1000 = 1200 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{EAC} &= \text{ETC} + \text{ACWP} \\ &= 1200 + 1100 = 2300 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

The definition of ETC and the qualitative evolution of costs are shown in the following figure.

In this figure, we highlight that the cost deviation observed in T_n remains at 100€ until the end of the project if the remaining work is performed as planned. At the control point T_n , the actual costs are below the budgeted costs that were supposed to be achieved, but they are above the budgeted costs realized. In this situation, the actual cost curve exceeds the budgeted costs because the project duration is longer than the initial estimate.

Chapter 5: Risk and Time Value of Money

Chapter Overview

This chapter covers the fundamentals of investment analysis. It illustrates how to quantify investment performance using concepts such as Return on Investment (ROI), and effective, nominal and continuous capitalization rates. It then presents the concept of risk and how investor risk aversion impacts decision-making. Finally, it explores the fundamental principle of time value of money, showing how to calculate the present and future value of cash flows and how to use Net Present Value (NPV) to evaluate projects.

5.1 Evaluating the Performance of an Investment

To present the parameters we use to assess investment performance, we will consider simple hypothetical situations, such as a bank deposit or the purchase and sale of securities in the capital markets. These concepts are also used to evaluate more complex situations, such as investments in physical projects (e.g., the construction of a factory) and decisions to create or acquire a company.

The investments that we consider below are characterized by requiring an initial amount of money I_0 , at the initial time, $t = 0$, and then providing Cash Flows C_i , in the following points in time, during the duration n of the investment ($i = 1, \dots, n$).

5.1.1. Return On Investment

Return On Investment (ROI) is often used to characterize investments that produce a unique outcome. In this case, it can be defined by the following expression (e.g. [5]):

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{\text{Profit}}{\text{Investment}}$$

To illustrate the application of this definition, consider the following example: the initial investment in a financial application is 1000 € and, two years from now, the investor can redeem his investment for 1400 €. In these conditions, considering $I_0 = 1000$ € and $C_2 = 1400$ € the expected profit is $L = C_2 - I_0 = 400$ € so, the expected ROI is given by:

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{400}{1000} = 0.4 \text{ (40\%)}$$

That is, in the end, our investment will have grown by 40%.

5.1.2. Effective Rate of Return

Taking the previous example as a reference, suppose that the financial application pays interest at the end of each year, which accrues to the application's value.

In this case, just after the initial investment, the value of the investment is: $V_0 = I_0 = 1000$ €, after one year it will be: $V_1 = V_0 + J_1$, where J_1 is the interest for the first year, and in the end it will be: $V_2 = V_1 + J_2 = 1400$ €, where J_2 is the interest for the second year.

Assuming that the investment contract offers the possibility of redemption at $t = 1$, receiving $C_1 = V_1$, or at $t = 2$, receiving $C_2 = V_2 = 1400$ €, we are interested in knowing how much we would receive if we decided to redeem the investment after one year.

To answer this question, the financial institutions that propose investments with these characteristics present in their proposal the return on investment, as we assessed previously, and also the effective rate of return, which allows us to answer the question.

To illustrate the calculation process, we consider the evolution of the investment value in the following figure:

So, we must first define how interest is assessed. Designating the effective rate by r (or r_{ef}), the interest assessed at a given time t is a function of the investment value at the previous time, as shown below:

$$J_t = rV_{t-1}$$

If interest accrues at the investment value, the investment value at time t is obtained from the following relationship:

$$V_t = V_{t-1} + J_t = (1+r)V_{t-1}$$

Therefore, for our example, we can establish the following relationships:

$$V_1 = (1+r)V_0$$

$$V_2 = (1+r)V_1$$

Combining the two expressions, we get:

$$V_2 = (1+r)^2 V_0$$

As we know the values of V_2 and V_0 , we can evaluate the value of r , as shown below:

$$r = \left(\frac{V_2}{V_0} \right)^{1/2} - 1 = 1.4^{0.5} - 1 = 0.1832 \quad (18.32\%)$$

Now, with the value of the effective rate, we can calculate the value of V_1 :

$$V_1 = (1+r)V_0 = 1.1832 \times 1000 = 1183.2 \text{ €}$$

That is, if we decide to redeem the investment after 1 year, we will receive $C_1 = 1183.2$ €.

$$\left(1 + \frac{r}{m}\right)^m = 1 + r$$

Where m designates the annual capitalization periodicity.

Continuing with the analysis of monthly capitalization, as we have already assessed the effective rate, the nominal rate for monthly capitalization can be assessed as shown below:

$$\frac{r_{12}}{12} = (1 + r)^{1/12} - 1 = 1.1832^{1/12} - 1 = 0.01412 \quad (1.412\%)$$

$$r_{12} = 0.01412 \times 12 = 0.1694 \quad (16.94\%)$$

Suppose now that we intend to redeem the investment after 5 months. To assess the amount that we would receive, we can perform the calculations using the nominal rate:

$$V_{m5} = \left(1 + \frac{r_{12}}{12}\right)^5 V_0 = 1.01412^5 \times 1000 = 1072.6 \text{ €}$$

However, due to the following relationship, we can also use the effective rate and obtain the same result, as shown below:

$$\left(1 + \frac{r_{12}}{12}\right)^5 = \left(\left(1 + \frac{r_{12}}{12}\right)^{12}\right)^{5/12} = (1 + r)^{5/12}$$

$$V_{m5} = (1 + r)^{5/12} V_0 = 1.1832^{5/12} \times 1000 = 1072.6 \text{ €}$$

5.1.4. Continuous Capitalization Rate of Return

Continuing with our study example, we can reduce the capitalization period to an infinitesimal interval of dt . To analyze this case, we present the following figure that illustrates what happens during that time interval.

The parameters presented in this figure are related to the expression shown below:

$$V_{t+dt} = V_t + dV_t = V_t + J_{dt}$$

This expression shows that the change in the investment value, dV_t , is equal to the interest generated, J_{dt} , during the time interval dt . On the other hand, the interest generated is defined by the expression:

$$J_{dt} = V_t r_c dt$$

Where r_c is the continuous capitalization rate (annualized) and dt is the time interval, expressed as a fraction of the year. In these conditions, the variation of the investment value, dV_t , is defined by the expression:

$$dV_t = V_t r_c dt$$

Considering the data of our example, we solve this differential equation, separating variables, and integrating between $t = 0$ and $t = 2$, where $V_0 = 1000$ and $V_2 = 1400$, as shown below:

$$\int_{V_0}^{V_2} \frac{dV_t}{V_t} = \int_0^2 r_c dt$$

The solution of the integration leads to the following result:

$$r_c = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{V_2}{V_0}\right) = 0.5 \ln(1.4) = 0.1682 \quad (16.82\%)$$

Taking into account that $V_2 = (1+r)^2 V_0$, we can conclude that we can also obtain r_c from the effective rate, as we illustrate in the following expression:

$$r_c = \ln(1+r) = \ln(1.1832) = 0.1682$$

If we consider an arbitrary time interval, from 0 to t , we obtain the following relationship between the initial value and the final value:

$$V_t = V_0 e^{r_c t}$$

Taking into account the results we obtained previously, we can now calculate again the value of the investment after 5 months, if the value of the investment is updated continuously, as illustrated below:

$$V_{m5} = 1000 \times \exp\left(0.1682 \frac{5}{12}\right) = 1072.6 \text{ €}$$

That is, the value is the same, but the two situations are not equivalent.

For example, if we tried to redeem the investment the day before completing 5 months, in the case of continuous capitalization, the amount received would be the following:

$$C_{m5'} = 1000 \times \exp\left(0.1682 \left(\frac{5}{12} - \frac{1}{365}\right)\right) = 1072.1 \text{ €}$$

However, in the case of monthly capitalization, the investment value is only recalculated once a month. Therefore, if we tried to redeem the investment 1 day before the interest of the fifth month matures, we would receive the accumulated value of the fourth month, which would be given by:

$$C_{m5'} = V_{m4} = \left(1 + \frac{r_{12}}{12}\right)^4 V_0 = 1.01412^4 \times 1000 = 1057.7 \text{ €}$$

5.2 Return and Risk

Most investment decisions in real projects or financial assets must be made knowing that the outcome is uncertain.

In view of the uncertainty about future financial results, decision-makers adopt different behaviors depending on their risk aversion. It is therefore important to have decision criteria for situations involving uncertainty and to characterize the influence of risk aversion in the assessment of a project's economic viability.

To characterize the decision criteria we will adopt in this discipline, we will use an example of a dice game. Thus, consider a game in which we roll a six-sided die, numbered from 1 to 6. To participate in this game, we have to put 50 € on the table for each roll of the dice. After the dice is rolled, if the result is 5 or 6, we receive 153 €, but if any other number comes out, we receive nothing.

If we consider playing this game for profit, the following questions arise. In the first place, it matters whether it is advantageous to play; then, even if it is, it matters whether we are willing to play.

To answer the first question, we evaluate the expected value of the possible results. If it is positive, it may be advantageous to play; if it is not, then we should not play.

To assess the expected value of possible outcomes, we must first determine the probabilities of success and failure.

Taking into account the rules of the game, the probability of success, which we represent by P_u , is equal to the probability of the set {5, 6}, and the probability of failure, P_d , is simply $1 - P_u$:

$$P_u = P\{5, 6\} = \frac{2}{6} = \frac{1}{3}$$

$$P_d = 1 - P_u = \frac{2}{3}$$

Before concluding the calculations on the first question, we can already say that these results will alienate many decision makers, because the probability of losing in each play is twice the probability of winning. Therefore, anyone with high risk aversion will not play this game, regardless of the conclusion we reach.

Continuing with the calculations, it is now important to evaluate all possible outcomes that result from the output of each face of the dice.

If the outcome is favorable, we will obtain a profit, L_u , and if it is unfavorable, it will be a loss, L_d , as we evaluate below:

$$\{5, 6\} \rightarrow L_u = C_u - I = 153 - 50 = 103 \text{ €}$$

$$\{1, 2, 3, 4\} \rightarrow L_d = C_d - I = 0 - 50 = -50 \text{ €}$$

With these results and with the value of the probabilities of occurrence, we evaluate the expected value of the profit, as we show below:

$$E[L] = \sum P_i L_i = P_u L_u + P_d L_d$$

$$= \frac{1}{3} \times 103 - \frac{2}{3} \times 50 = 1 \text{ €}$$

In view of this result, we cannot say that it is not worth playing this game.

However, if we only have 50 € to play once, it would be advisable not to play, because the probability of the first outcome being favorable is small.

Nevertheless, if we have capital to play many times, and if the dice are not defective, as we will see, it is advantageous to play. For example, in six moves, if the faces that occurred obey the statistics, we could have the outcomes that we present in the following table:

i	l	Ci	L=Ci-l
1	50	0	-50
2	50	0	-50
3	50	0	-50
4	50	0	-50
5	50	153	103
6	50	153	103
	300	306	6

Even with risk aversion, we can still affirm that, for a small number of moves, there is no guarantee that the outcomes will obey the statistics, as presented in this table.

However, if we consider many more moves, this argument no longer makes sense.

Therefore, if the decision maker must make many decisions involving uncertainty and has only information about expected value, he should accept investments with a positive expected profit.

If the decision-maker has capital constraints, he can introduce other criteria to decide which projects to accept at the expense of others.

To characterize the behavior of the individual investor, we will now model risk aversion.

Risk Aversion

Risk aversion can be accounted for by introducing a utility function, $U(x)$, which defines the level of investor satisfaction. It is a continuous, increasing function with a decreasing derivative. The following family of functions meets these conditions:

$$U(x) = x^{1/\alpha}$$

where $\alpha > 1$. This parameter is a constant that is higher the greater the degree of risk aversion. To apply this concept to our study example, we have to compare the utility of the amount invested in the bet with the utility of the expected value of the bet outcome, as shown below, for the case of $\alpha = 1.2$:

$$U(I) = 50^{1/1.2} = 26.05$$

$$U(C_u) = 153^{1/1.2} = 66.16$$

$$U(C_d) = 0$$

$$E[U(C)] = P_d \times U(C_d) + P_u \times U(C_u) = 0 + \frac{1}{3} \times 66.16 = 22.05$$

Therefore, as the relationship $U(I) > E[U(C)]$ is verified, the investor, with this level of risk aversion, does not invest, preferring to keep the investment money. So, to attract this investor, for this game, we would have to decrease the initial investment, maintaining the result in the case of success, in order to verify the following relationship:

$$U(I_\alpha) = E[U(C)] \Rightarrow I_\alpha^{1/1.2} = 22.05 \Leftrightarrow I_\alpha = 41 \text{ €}$$

In other words, a consequence of risk aversion can be a reduction in the investment required to attract investors.

In a business context, it is often interesting to compare investment alternatives with different levels of risk. In these situations, it is convenient to conduct a relative comparison based on return on investment.

If we do not consider risk aversion, the expected return on investment is evaluated as shown below:

we can determine first the expected value of the money received:

$$\begin{aligned} E[C] &= \sum P_i C_i = P_u C_u + P_d C_d \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \times 153 + \frac{2}{3} \times 0 = 51 \text{ €} \end{aligned}$$

and then we evaluate the expected return as shown below:

$$E[R] = \frac{E[C] - I}{I} = \frac{51 - 50}{50} = 0.02 \quad (2\%)$$

However, if we consider risk aversion, the expected return on investment, for $\alpha = 1.2$, will be:

$$E[R] = \frac{E[C] - I_\alpha}{I_\alpha} = \frac{51 - 41}{41} = 0.24 \quad (24\%)$$

Therefore, from this example, a business proposal with uncertain results, if it wants to attract typical investors, has to lower the initial investment value to increase the expected profitability.

5.3 Time Value of Money

When we invest in a financial application, we are exchanging today's Euros for future Euros. In simplified terms, we give up consuming part today with the expectation of being able to consume more tomorrow. Likewise, when we ask for a bank loan to invest in a project or to finance a vacation, we accept that we will have to pay more in the future for the amount we receive today to use as we wish.

In both cases, we are dealing with exchanges of cash flows spread over different periods, but these exchanges obey the following rule: a future cash flow exchanged for a current cash flow must have a higher value (e.g. [5]).

However, to quantify the value of these exchanges, we must first consider two situations: investing without risk and investing with risk.

Risk-free investment

In an ideal situation with no risk to investors, the cost of financing would equal the return on financial investments. Consequently, under this ideal situation, we could exchange today's Euros for tomorrow's Euros to finance our needs without additional opportunity costs of capital.

To illustrate the consequences of these hypotheses, let us consider two elementary examples.

We first consider the possibility of investing $I_0 = 1000$ € for 1 year at an effective rate of 10%, with the promise of receiving $C_1 = 1100$ € at the end. We say that this value is the future value of the amount invested. In this situation, we define the Future Value (FV) from the following expressions:

$$\begin{cases} FV(I_0) = C_1 \\ C_1 = I_0(1+r) \end{cases} \rightarrow FV(I_0) = I_0(1+r) = 1000 \times 1.1 = 1100 \text{ €}$$

On the other hand, if we need $C_0 = 1000$ € today and use a bank loan for a year at a 10% capital cost, we would have to repay $C_1 = 1100$ € in one year. In this case, we say that the amount we would receive today is the present value of the amount we will have to return in the future. So, we define the Present Value (PV) from the following expressions:

$$\begin{cases} C_0 = PV(C_1) \\ C_1 = C_0(1+r) \end{cases} \rightarrow PV(C_1) = \frac{C_1}{1+r} = \frac{1100}{1.1} = 1000 \text{ €}$$

Returning to the situation where we deposit 1000 € for the duration of one year, at an effective rate of 10%, we define the Net Present Value (NPV) of this investment, using the following expression:

$$NPV = -I_0 + \frac{C_1}{1+r}$$

Using the data from the example, we obtain:

$$NPV = -1000 + \frac{1100}{1.1} = 0$$

This result means that the value of the investment equals the present value of the future benefits it will provide.

In this case, the rate of return on the investment is used to convert the future receipt into its present value.

Although we are considering an ideal situation – namely, the absence of risk – this principle still holds even in real situations where future results are uncertain.

Investment with risk

When risk is introduced, we also say that the value of the investment equals the present value of the future benefits it will generate. However, in this case, the discount rate used to assess the present value of future benefits should reflect the uncertainty associated with those benefits, not the expected return on the investment.

In the face of uncertainty, the viability of an investment is assessed by comparing its benefits with those of other investments of equivalent risk. Consequently, if the expected return on investment is identical to the opportunity cost of capital of alternative investments and the risk is identical, the investment's NPV will be approximately nil.

To illustrate the decision process, when we introduce risk due to uncertainty, we consider a simple example in which we have the opportunity to invest 900 € in a financial application that will provide a cash flow in a year from now, depending on the occurrence of a future event related, for example, to the climate.

So, the future cash flow of the project will be $C_{1d} = 900$ € if next summer's average temperature is lower than this summer's, and $C_{1u} = 1300$ € otherwise. Additionally, based on recent temperature trends, it is not possible to favor either scenario, so the outcome probabilities will be the same for both the favorable (up) and unfavorable (down) scenarios: $P_u = P_d = 0.5$.

Under these conditions, the expected value of the future receipt is evaluated as shown below:

$$E[C_1] = P_u C_{1u} + P_d C_{1d} = 0.5 \times 900 + 0.5 \times 1300 = 1100 \text{ €}$$

Based on the concept we initially presented (in the game example), we cannot immediately exclude this investment from our list of possibilities because the expected profit is positive (200 €).

To analyze under which conditions it is advantageous to maintain this investment, we consider the following scenarios, having as a reference the profitability provided by the investment:

$$E[R] = \frac{E[C_1] - I_0}{I_0} = \frac{1100 - 900}{900} = 0.222$$

i) If the opportunity cost of capital, in other investment alternatives, with an equivalent level of risk, is 22.2% (i.e., if we have $r = E[R]$), the NPV of the investment will be:

$$NPV = -I_0 + \frac{E[C_1]}{1+r} = -900 + \frac{1100}{1.222} = 0$$

With this result, if we have no capital restrictions, we maintain the decision to invest in this financial investment.

ii) If the opportunity cost of capital, in other investment alternatives, of equivalent level of risk, is 15%, the NPV of the investment will be:

$$NPV = -900 + \frac{1100}{1.15} = 56.52 \text{ €}$$

In this case, we should invest in this financial application. If there is liquidity, we could immediately sell the financial application for a value determined from the “fair price” relation:

$$NPV_m = -I_m + \frac{1100}{1.15} = 0 \rightarrow I_m = I_0 + NPV = 956.5 \text{ €}$$

In other words, in these circumstances we would be able to invest 900 € in a financial application and sell it right away for 956.5 €, without any risk.

iii) If the opportunity cost of capital, i.e. the expected reward in other investment alternatives, of equivalent risk level, is 30%, we should not put money in this application because it would be $NPV < 0$:

$$NPV = -900 + \frac{1100}{1.3} = -53.9 \text{ €}$$

Suppose we mistakenly invested in this application. We identify the error too late and now we need the money to invest in an alternative financial application. In this case, we have to recognize the loss of -53.9 €, corresponding to the discount we would have to apply to sell our position. Under these conditions, the fair price would be:

$$I_m = I_0 + NPV = 900 - 53.9 = 846.1 \text{ €}$$

So, we must cancel our investment position if losses are expected to worsen or if we identify better opportunities to apply the 846.1 € redemption amount.

5.4 Application Examples

Example 5.4.1

Calculate the NPV and the return on investment (ROI) for each of the investments shown in the following table, knowing that the opportunity cost of capital is 20% for all. Also, analyze the following questions, identifying the best decision (adapted from [5]).

- The investor has only 10,000 € available, but can only choose one of the projects.
- The investor has only 10,000 € available and can invest in more than one project (the projects are unique and are not fractionable).
- The investor has only 10,000 € available, and there are multiple equal projects.
- The projects are unique and are not fractionable, but the investor has no money limitations and can invest in more than one project.

Inv	C0=-I0	C1
A	-10000	20000
B	-5000	12000
C	-5000	5500
D	-2000	5000

Solution

The calculations necessary to answer the questions asked involve the following expressions, which define the value of the return on investment (R) and the NPV:

$$R = \frac{C_1 - I_0}{I_0} = \frac{L}{I_0}$$

$$NPV = -I_0 + \frac{C_1}{1+r}$$

Considering that the opportunity cost of capital is 20%, we obtain the results presented in the following table:

Inv	C0=-I0	C1	NPV	R%	L
A	-10000	20000	6666.7	100	10000
B	-5000	12000	5000.0	140	7000
C	-5000	5500	-416.7	10	500
D	-2000	5000	2166.7	150	3000

To answer the questions posed in tasks a, b, c, and d, we need to consider the NPV values.

- If the investor can only choose one of the projects and if he has 10,000 € available, he must choose the project with the highest NPV, i.e., Project A.

The NPV equals the potential profit that can be realized if the project is sold immediately after acquisition. It represents the immediate potential increase in investor wealth.

- The projects are unique and are not fractionable, and the investor has 10,000 € available. In this case, the investor must acquire projects B and D to maximize the

investment's total NPV. The NPV values are today's Euros and can be added. By investing in B and D, the investor can immediately increase his wealth by 7166.7 €.

c) The investor has 10,000 € available and there are multiple identical projects. Under these conditions, the solution that maximizes the NPV of the total investment is to acquire 5 type D projects. In this case, the NPV for a total investment of 10,000 € is 10833.3 €. Under these conditions, the investor could have doubled his wealth immediately.

d) If the projects are unique and are not divisible, and the investor has no money limitations, he would buy projects A, B, and D and reject project C, because it has a negative NPV.

A negative NPV indicates that the requested investment is excessive, given the defined risk level. It represents a potential loss if the project is sold to another investor.

Example 5.4.2

We intend to start a savings plan to buy a boat within 5 years. The boat will cost 20,000€, and we can invest our savings in a financial application with an effective annual rate of return of 10% (adapted from [5]).

- What is the amount to be deposited at the end of each year to collect the necessary money?
- What should be the monthly deposit if we choose monthly capitalization?
- What should be the value of the single deposit at $t = 0$ that would lead to the same result?

Solution

a) In order to determine the amount we have to deposit in our bank account at the end of each year, to add the necessary 20,000 €, we can analyze the evolution in time of the value of each deposit.

We will designate the value of each deposit by C , and we will start by analyzing the evolution of the first deposit.

Suppose we are now at the beginning of the first year; we will deposit the value C at $t = 1$, i.e., at the end of the year. Each year that passes, the deposited amount earns interest at the effective rate r , which accumulates in the account balance. In this way, we conclude that the value deposited at the end of the first year ($t = 1$) will be multiplied by the factor $(1 + r)$ four times until we reach $t = 5$, transforming it into $C(1 + r)^4$.

The second deposit, made at $t = 2$, is multiplied by the same factor, but less once time, and so on until the fifth deposit, which does not transform, because it is withdrawn shortly afterwards, together with the accumulated value of the other deposits, to buy the boat. Thus, the final amount in our bank account can be defined by the following expression:

$$FV = C\left(1 + (1+r) + (1+r)^2 + (1+r)^3 + (1+r)^4\right)$$

Noting that the terms in parentheses are in geometric progression, we can resort to the expression of the sum of n terms of a geometric progression, S_n , to simplify the previous expression.

$$S_n = a_1 \frac{1 - \rho^n}{1 - \rho}$$

Considering the ratio $\rho = (1+r)$, the first term is $a_1 = 1$, and $n = 5$, we get:

$$FV = C \frac{1 - (1+r)^5}{1 - (1+r)} = C \frac{(1+r)^5 - 1}{r}$$

Introducing the problem data in this expression, we obtain:

$$20000 = C \frac{1.1^5 - 1}{0.1} \Leftrightarrow 20000 = C \times 6.1051$$

So we get $C = 3275.95 \text{ €}$.

The total amount deposited in the account is $C \times 5 = 16379.75 \text{ €}$, and the accrued interest is $FV - C \times 5 = 3620.25 \text{ €}$.

b) This question is identical to the previous one, but now savings are made every month in an account with monthly capitalization. In this case, the deposited amount earns interest each month, which accrues to the account balance.

The monthly interest rate can be determined from the effective rate, but it is not equal to the effective rate divided by 12. The monthly interest rate equals the nominal monthly capitalization rate, r_m , divided by 12.

The following expression gives the relationship between the nominal rate and the effective rate:

$$\left(1 + \frac{r_m}{12}\right)^{12} = 1 + r$$

As we know $r = 10\%$, we obtain the monthly interest rate first:

$$\frac{r_m}{12} = (1 + r)^{1/12} - 1 = 1.1^{1/12} - 1 = 0.007974$$

Moreover, annualizing the monthly rate, we get the nominal rate:

$$r_m = 0.007974 \times 12 = 0.0957 \quad (9.57\%)$$

To determine the monthly installment, we can use an expression identical to that of the previous question to assess the future value of savings.

In the previous case, the savings were annual, the rate was annual, and the number of capitalizations equaled the number of years. Likewise, we will now have monthly

savings, a monthly rate, and the number of capitalizations equal to the number of months. Considering that 5 years is 60 months, we get:

$$FV = C_m \frac{(1 + r_m/12)^{60} - 1}{r_m/12}$$

Using the expression that relates the nominal rate to the effective rate, we can simplify this expression to obtain the following:

$$FV = C_m \frac{(1 + r)^5 - 1}{r_m/12}$$

Entering the problem data, we obtain:

$$20000 = C_m \frac{1.1^5 - 1}{0.007974} \Leftrightarrow 20000 = C_m \times 76.561$$

So we get $C_m = 261.23 \text{ €}$.

The total amount deposited in the account is $C_m \times 60 = 15673.80 \text{ €}$, and the accrued interest is $FV - C_m \times 60 = 4326.20 \text{ €}$.

c) To determine the value of the single deposit C_0 , which leads to the same result, we consider that the price of the boat is the future value of C_0 , that is:

$$C_0 (1 + r)^5 = FV \Leftrightarrow C_0 = \frac{FV}{(1 + r)^5}$$

Entering the problem data, we obtain:

$$C_0 = \frac{20000}{1.1^5} = 12418.43 \text{ €}$$

Moreover, the accrued interest is 7581.57 € .

Chapter 6: Investment Valuation

Chapter Overview

This chapter presents the main techniques used to evaluate investment opportunities and determine their economic viability. It discusses the concepts of cash flow, discount rate, and opportunity cost of capital, introducing key financial indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and Payback Period. Through illustrative examples, it shows how these tools support decision-making by comparing alternative projects under different risk and return conditions.

6.1 Investment Valuation Criteria

The economic viability of an investment project can be assessed by considering a set of assumptions, not only those related to its implementation, but also those regarding the behavior of external variables whose evolution over time is uncertain.

We will now analyze several criteria commonly used to decide whether to accept an investment project. However, the only criterion for assessing the economic viability of a project with an economic foundation, which we are going to analyze, is that of the Net Present Value (e.g. [5]).

The Net Present Value criterion is not only economically sound but also based on forecasts of the relative behavior of the project's activity compared to other existing projects in the same sector of economic activity.

6.1.1 Net Present Value

The Net Present Value (NPV) criterion states that a project is viable if it improves the investor's economic and financial position, given that the investor faces multiple investment alternatives with varying levels of risk.

To decide whether a project is viable, the investor needs to evaluate the NPV and determine whether it is non-negative. If the NPV is equal to zero, the investment in the project is fair and reflects the opportunity cost of Capital in other projects of equivalent risk. If the NPV is greater than zero, the project is an excellent opportunity and, if there are no other restrictions, it should be purchased.

Despite the simplicity of the description of the decision process, in practice, using this criterion is neither simple nor easy.

Implementing this criterion assumes that reliable forecasts of the project's cash flows throughout its economic life are available. It is also necessary to assess the appropriate opportunity cost of Capital. This should reflect both the time value of money and the project's risk.

On the other hand, the concept of the opportunity cost of Capital assumes that assets with an equivalent level of risk can be compared. This assumption is valid if the investor has access to the capital markets (i.e., knows how to intervene in them).

In this context, the discount rate is the opportunity cost of investing in the project, relative to investing in the capital market. Because instead of accepting the project, the investor can invest in financial assets.

Despite the underlying assumptions not always being met, the NPV criterion has the advantage of depending solely on the project's projected cash flows and the opportunity cost of Capital.

This characteristic is important because investment analysis criteria may depend on the decision-maker's preferences, the accounting methods used, the profitability of the company's current activity, or the profitability of other projects that may not be comparable. In these cases, the decision is not objective because the same information does not always lead to the same result. In these cases, the final result is established beforehand, and the criteria that justify it are then chosen.

Relevant Cash Flows

The Cash flows relevant to the evaluation of a project are those generated by the project and incremental (e.g. [5]), in the sense that they appear only after the project has started operating.

Because the net result shown in the project's income statement is based on financial accounting rules, it is important to realize that this parameter is not a cash flow. Its value is influenced by depreciation, which represents the imputation of a cost for using the assets. Economically, they represent the savings from the cost of self-financing asset renewal. So, depreciation on the project's assets should be excluded, but the tax savings they generate should be included (since they do not represent financing).

Funding and investment in the project must be separated (e.g. [5]). The debt capital used to finance the project results in tax savings that should be excluded, because the project's viability should not depend on its financing. To illustrate the application of these principles, we present the following example: we evaluate a single cash flow for a project using its income statement for the same period.

Income Statement		Cash-Flow	
Sales	100	Sales	100
Cost of Sales	-70	Cost of Sales	-70
Depreciation	-10	Depreciation	-10
EBIT	20	EBT	20
Interest	-10	Taxes (30%)	-6
EBT	10	EAT	14
Taxes (30%)	-3	Depreciation	10
NI	7	CF	24

In this process, we emphasize that when assessing cash flow, depreciation is initially subtracted from sales to assess the tax savings it provides, and then added back at the end, because it does not actually represent an outflow of money. The outflow of money that gives rise to the depreciation is the investment that is fully accounted for in the NPV assessment. We can also see that the interest recorded in the income statement on debt capital used to finance the project is ignored when assessing cash flow.

Free Cash Flow

The cash flow illustrated in the previous example results from the project's operations and is therefore referred to as operational cash flow.

Due to differences between the payment and receipt periods, it may be necessary to save part of the cash flow generated in one year to offset payments with shorter maturities in the following year.

The amount of cash flow that must be saved to offset future payments, with an average term shorter than that of receipts, is called Working Capital. The part of the cash flow that is not necessary to reserve is called Free Cash Flow.

When working capital changes are relevant, the cash flows we use to assess the project are called Free Cash Flows.

To illustrate the process of evaluating Free Cash Flows, let us consider the example illustrated in the following figure. The figure shows that the project's operational cash flow over the next 3 years is constant at 100 k€. Cash flows in blue that represent receipts, and cash flows in red that represent payments, are also presented, the balance of which is zero.

As the first payment of 20 k€ occurs before the first receipt of 20 k€, which cancels it, it is necessary to reserve 20 k€ of the first operational cash flow to make the first payment. Under these conditions, the 20 k€ represented in blue are transferred to the second operational cash flow.

The result of these adjustments is shown in the following figure:

This figure illustrates the release of positive flows to offset negative flows and identifies free cash flows for each year: 80, 90, and 130 k€, totaling the initial amount of 300 k€.

To account for working capital needs, we need to define them for each year. In general, working capital needs are part of the problem data, and if they are not mentioned, they are considered negligible.

In the example we have presented, the working capital needs for each year are the negative cash flows shown in red. Free cash flow can be determined from the operating cash flow and the working capital variation using the following expression:

$$CF_t = CFo_t - \Delta WC_t$$

The following table illustrates the procedure for evaluating the free cash flows:

	0	1	2	3
WC	0	20	30	0
ΔWC	0	20	10	-30
CFo	0	100	100	100
CF	0	80	90	130

6.1.2 Payback Period

The payback period of a project is the number of years required for the estimated cash flows to equal the initial investment. The following expression translates this idea into mathematical terms:

$$PB = \text{Min}(T) : \sum_{t=1}^T CF_t \geq I$$

To use the payback period criterion to decide whether to accept a project, the investor must define an appropriate cutoff period. However, the most attractive projects will be those with the shortest payback periods. And, if the investor uses the same limit regardless of the project's lifetime, there will be a tendency to accept many short-life projects and very few long-life projects. So, if, on average, the time limits are too long, the investor (individual or institutional) will be led to accept some projects with negative NPV; and, if, on average, the cutoff periods are too short, the investor will reject some projects with positive NPV.

The payback period gives equal weight to all cash flows before the recovery date and none to those after it.

One problem with the payback period criterion is that it does not account for the time value of money. To work around this limitation, we can define a discounted payback period, in which cash flows are discounted before the payback period is calculated. The payback period in this case represents the time necessary for the project to be acceptable in terms of NPV. However, this version of the method continues to disregard cash flows that occur after the cutoff period.

The following table (adapted from [5]) presents data for three projects and the results of the payback period and NPV assessments, assuming an opportunity cost of Capital of 10%.

	C0	C1	C2	C3	PB	NPV
A	-2000	2000	200		1	-16.53
B	-2000	1000	1000	1000	2	486.85
C	-2000	750	750	2000	3	804.28

The problem data was chosen to highlight the contradictions of this criterion. For example, project A has the smallest PB, but, according to the NPV criterion, it is economically unviable. Project C has the highest NPV but also the largest PB.

6.1.3 Internal Rate of Return

The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is the rate of return that makes NPV equal to zero. When it exists, it can be determined from the following equation:

$$NPV = -I + \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{C_t}{(1 + IRR)^t} = 0$$

When used as a decision criterion, the rule is to accept the project if the opportunity cost of Capital is less than the internal rate of return. When comparing the opportunity cost of Capital with the IRR, we are effectively asking whether the NPV is positive. If the NPV is a decreasing function of the discount rate, $IRR \geq r$ it is equivalent to $NPV \geq 0$, but the NPV is not always a well-behaved function. For this reason, there are many situations in which the internal rate of return criterion yields incorrect results.

The following figure shows the NPV for project C from the previous table as a function of the discount rate. This is an example where the NPV is a well-behaved function of the discount rate, with an IRR of 27.91%.

To analyze situations in which the IRR criterion can lead to inconsistent results, the following table (adapted from [5]) presents data for four projects and the results of the IRR and NPV assessments, assuming a 10% opportunity cost of Capital.

	C0	C1	C2	C3	IRR	NPV
D	1000	-3600	4320	-1728	0.2	-0.75
E	1000	-3000	4000	-2050	0.05	38.32
F	1000	-3000	4000	-1950		113.45
G	-1000	6250	-6250		0.25 & 4	-483.47

The first three projects generate positive cash flow initially. This situation can occur in remodeling projects where, for example, equipment that will be replaced is sold first.

As the table shows, the first project has an IRR of 20%, but with an opportunity cost of Capital of 10%, it is not economically viable. The evolution of the NPV of this project with the discount rate is shown in the following figure. From this figure, we can conclude that, in this case, the project is feasible only for discount rates above the IRR, whereas in project C, the opposite is true.

Evolution of the NPV of project D

Project F has no IRR; the NPV is positive for any value of the opportunity cost of Capital.

Project G has two IRR solutions. Analyzing the evolution of the NPV with the discount rate, we concluded that this project would be viable if the discount rate falls between the IRR and a second value.

Evolution of the NPV of project G

6.2 NPV Application Example

The predicted net results of a project are shown in the following table (adapted from [5]). The project requires an initial investment of 10 million Euros in manufacturing facilities and equipment, which is shown in the first line of the table.

The investment will be depreciated over 6 years, considering a residual book value of 500 thousand Euros. However, the plant's net residual value was estimated at 1.95 million Euros. The corresponding annual depreciations are $9.5/6 = 1.5833$ million Euros. The difference between the estimated residual value and the residual book value is a taxable profit.

We intend to evaluate the project's NPV, assuming the opportunity cost of Capital, appropriate to the project's risk, is 20%.

To assess the NPV, we need to determine the project's cash flows from the income statement data. However, it is also important to first interpret the information presented in the table. The initial investment appears in row 1, in the column for $t = 0$, where other

costs also appear in row 6. These costs are also part of the initial investment, but they relate to the non-depreciable portion.

The time horizon is extended here to $t = 6.25$ because we assume it takes 3 months to dismantle and sell the facilities at the residual value shown in the first row, last column.

Non-depreciable costs at $t = 0$ give rise to a loss before taxes, resulting in tax savings (negative taxes) because we assume the project is inserted in an institution that has profits from other activities. Consequently, the loss recorded in this project will result in tax savings for other activities.

Forecasts of the results (thousands of Euros)								
Period	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	6.25
1. Investment	-10000							1950
2. Year-end book value	10000	8417	6833	5250	3667	2083	500	500
3. Working capital		550	1289	3261	4890	3583	2002	0
4. Sales		523	12887	32610	48901	35834	19717	
5. COGS		837	7729	19552	29345	21492	11830	
6. Other costs	4000	2200	1210	1331	1464	1611	1772	
7. Depreciation		1583	1583	1583	1583	1583	1583	
8. EBT (4-5-6-7)	-4000	-4097	2365	10144	16509	11148	4532	1450
9. Taxes at 34%	-1360	-1393	804	3449	5613	3790	1541	493
10. EAT (8-9)	-2640	-2704	1561	6695	10896	7357	2991	957

As the presented income statement does not include information on financial charges for loans, the values of the operational cash flow can be obtained from the values of the earnings after taxes (EAT) presented in line 10, adding the values of the depreciation, presented in line 7, and the residual book value, presented in the last column of row 2.

Free cash flow is obtained by subtracting the change in working Capital from operating cash flow, as assessed based on the results presented in line 3.

Period	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	6.25
WC	0	550	1289	3261	4890	3583	2002	0
ΔWC	0	550	739	1972	1629	-1307	-1581	-2002
EAT	-2640	-2704	1561	6695	10896	7357	2991	957
Depreciation	0	1583	1583	1583	1583	1583	1583	500
CF	-2640	-1671	2405	6306	10850	10248	6155	3459

Based on the information presented in the last line of the previous table, we can evaluate the project's NPV, as shown below:

$$NPV = -12\,640 - \frac{1671}{1.2} + \frac{2405}{1.2^2} + \frac{6306}{1.2^3} + \frac{10850}{1.2^4} + \frac{10248}{1.2^5} + \frac{6155}{1.2^6} + \frac{3459}{1.2^{6.25}} = 3806 \text{ k€}$$

Therefore, since the NPV is positive, the project is economically viable.

6.3 Financial Maps

The financial maps present accounting information about the companies. There are three types of maps: the Balance Sheet, the Income Statement, and the Cash Flow Statement.

The balance sheet presents a company's Equity and financial position as of a given date, showing its assets, liabilities, and the position of its owners. The Income Statement explains how the company generated Net Income over a given period. The Cash Flow Statement explains changes in Equity and the sources and uses of funds.

Financial maps are important in project management because evaluating the project's economic viability involves determining the project's costs and future benefits to the company.

In this discipline, we will analyze only the Balance Sheet and the Income Statement.

In the first place, we are interested in establishing the relationship between the evolution of the balance sheet and the income statement. It is also important to identify the purpose of depreciation and its effect on net Income. It also allows introducing the concepts of return on assets and return on Equity, and identifying the effect of the project's financing structure on these indicators.

6.3.1 Balance Sheet

The book values on the company's equity status are recorded in three types of accounts: the Assets accounts, the Liabilities (or Debt) accounts, and the Equity accounts.

The Assets records the company's assets and rights. It is an indicator of a company's size. The Liabilities represent the company's obligations and debts. It includes bank loans, debts to suppliers, debts to the state, etc. The difference between Assets and Liabilities represents the Equity, which is the company's net worth.

From a financial perspective, the Assets are the source of capital investments and the Liabilities, together with the Equity, are the sources of financing.

Main Assets items

Asset accounts are divided into short-term, medium-term and long-term assets.

In short-term assets, we highlight Cash, Credits on Third Parties (e.g., merchandise sold and not yet paid), and Stocks (e.g., finished products awaiting sale).

In the medium and long-term assets we can include financial investments (e.g., bank deposits and securities) and fixed assets (e.g., equipment, buildings, and land).

Main items of Liabilities

Liabilities (or Debt) accounts represent the company's debts, which are one of its sources of funds. There are two main categories: short-term liabilities and medium and long-term liabilities.

Short-term liabilities are debts due within 1 year, such as those to suppliers. Medium and long-term liabilities are debts due in more than one year, such as bank loans and debt securities (e.g., bonds) issued by the company.

Equity

The Equity accounts represent the accounting position of the company's owners (or the company's book value). There are three categories: Capital, Reserves, and Net Income.

Capital represents the values with which shareholders initially entered the company and the changes that have occurred since then.

Reserves are funds accumulated by the company for future investments or to address adverse situations that may arise. They can have several origins, such as from profits and re-evaluations.

The Net Income represents the profit or loss generated by the company during the year. If it is positive, it can be reinvested or distributed to shareholders.

The Fundamental Balance Sheet Equation

The Assets account represents the company's total investment in resources. The sources of funds are Liabilities and Equity. Since the total amount of funds invested must be equal to the total amount of funds' sources, we obtain:

$$\text{Assets} = \text{Debt} + \text{Equity}$$

The following figure shows the main items of the company's balance sheet:

Balance Sheet	
<u>Assets</u>	<u>Liabilities</u>
<u>Current Assets</u>	<u>Current Liabilities</u>
Cash	Accounts Payable
Accounts receivable	Bank Loans Payable
Inventories	Other Creditors
<u>Fixed Assets</u>	<u>Long term Liabilities</u>
Property Land & Equipment	Bank Loans
	Issued debts securities
	<u>Equity</u>
	Capital
	Reserves
	Retained earnings
	Net Income

6.3.2 Income Statement

The income statement explains how the company generated the Net Income.

Shareholders are not interested in knowing only whether they have made a profit or a loss; they are also interested in how this result was generated, what the revenues were, and what costs the company incurred.

The Net Income is the profit or loss obtained during a given economic period, and it is defined as the difference between revenues and costs:

$$\text{Net Income} = \text{Revenues} - \text{Costs}$$

Revenues occur with the provision of a service or the sale of goods. They represent an improvement in shareholders' position: as the result increases, Equity increases as well.

Costs arise when goods are consumed or assets or services are used. They are generally associated with revenues and correspond to everything that the company used and consumed to generate those revenues. They represent a decrease in Equity.

The Income Statement is not limited to distinguishing costs and revenues; it also classifies them by origin, distinguishing three components: Operating Result, Financial Result, and Extraordinary Result.

The Operating Result corresponds to the portion of the Income obtained from the company's operating activity. It is a function of two fundamental components: the Sales

Margin and the Sales Volume. The Financial Result arises from the exercise of the company's financial function. It is usually only important in highly indebted companies. The Extraordinary Result records events that, by their nature, are infrequent, such as the sale of fixed assets, losses from floods and fires, etc.

To assess profitability indicators and determine the economic viability of the project, we present the Income Statement according to the model below.

Income Statement
Sales and Other Operating revenues
- Cost of Sales (COGS)
- Other operating costs
- Depreciation
OPERATING RESULT
+ Result from financial investments
+ Extraordinary Result
EARNINGS BEFORE INTEREST AND TAXES (EBIT)
- Interest
EARNINGS BEFORE TAXES (EBT)
- Taxes
NET INCOME (NI)

Case Study 1

To illustrate the application of these notes, let us consider a simple example related to the creation of a new company.

The company was formed at the beginning of last year ($t = 0$) by two partners and aims to buy clothes from producers and sell them to resellers.

To start operations, the company bought a vehicle to transport goods right at the beginning, which cost € 10,000.

The partners entered the company with equal Capital, which totaled € 5000. To raise the Capital needed to purchase the vehicle, they applied (on behalf of the company) for a bank loan of € 5000, with an effective interest rate of 10% per year.

Regarding loan repayments, there is total flexibility, with the company only obliged to pay interest on the outstanding Capital in each period.

The vehicle's amortization period is 5 years.

Based on these data, we can present the company's balance sheet at the beginning of the year, immediately after the vehicle purchase.

Considering that all the money that entered the company was used to buy the vehicle, in the Assets part, the value in Cash is null, and the value of Fixed Assets is € 10000.

In Liabilities (or Debt), we record the Bank Loan at € 5000.

In Equity, we registered in Capital the value of € 5000, for two shares ($nc = 2$). In Reserves and Net Income, we do not record anything because there are no values yet.

These values are summarized in the following table:

Balance Sheet (t = 0)			
Assets		Liabilities	
Cash	0	Bank Loan	5000
Fixed Assets	10000	Equity	
		Capital	5000
		Reserves	0
		Net Income	0
	10000		10000

This table is compatible with the fundamental balance sheet equation, which states that Assets are equal to Liabilities (or Debt) plus Shareholders' Equity, that is:

$$A_0 = D_0 + E_0$$

At the end of last year (t = 1), the company made its first income statement and recorded the following information:

1. Sales worth € 5000, with costs of € 1000
2. Vehicle depreciation: € 2000
3. Interest paid to the bank on the Capital owed: € 500
4. Taxes paid to the state on profits, at the rate of 20% : € 300

With this information and based on the model previously presented, we can reconstruct the income statement table.

Its acquisition value and economic life define the vehicle's depreciation. As the vehicle cost € 10,000, no residual value V_r was defined, and since the economic life is 5 years, we obtain:

$$Dep = \frac{I - V_r}{n_e} = \frac{10000 - 0}{5} = 2000 \text{ € / year}$$

The amount of interest paid, J, is obtained as shown below:

$$J = BL \times r = 5000 \times 0.1 = \text{€ } 500$$

To determine the taxes paid, we must first determine the earnings before taxes:

$$\begin{aligned} EBT &= Sales - Costs \\ &= Sales - COGS - Dep - Int \end{aligned}$$

Introducing the problem data, we get:

$$EBT = 5000 - 1000 - 2000 - 500 = \text{€ } 1500$$

Under these conditions, the amount of taxes that is due this year is:

$$Tax = EBT \times t = 1500 \times 0.2 = \text{€ } 300$$

The after-tax earnings (i.e., the net Income) can then be assessed as shown below:

$$NI = EBT - Tax = 1500 - 300 = \text{€ } 1200$$

This sequence of calculations can be presented in a table like the one shown below:

Income Statement (t = 1)	
Sales	5000
COGS	-1000
Depreciation	-2000
EBIT	2000
Interest	-500
EBT	1500
Taxes	-300
NI	1200

From the balance sheet at $t = 0$ and the income statement for the first year, we can construct the balance sheet at $t = 1$.

Considering Assets in the first place, we start by calculating Cash, taking into account the transactions carried out, as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} Cash_1 &= Sales - COGS - Int - Tax \\ &= 5000 - 1000 - 500 - 300 = \text{€ } 3200 \end{aligned}$$

That is, the value of sales is subtracted from the amounts paid.

As depreciation is not actually paid, it is not included in these calculations.

Depreciation is accounted for in the reduction of Fixed Assets, as shown below:

$$FixAss_1 = FixAss_0 - Dep_1 = 10000 - 2000 = \text{€ } 8000$$

Regarding Liabilities, there are no changes because we only pay interest on the money we receive; that is, we do not amortize anything on the loan.

Regarding Equity, the Capital item does not change because the partners did not add more money, and the Reserves item does not change either because no money has yet been set aside for it. The Net Income item receives the NI amount determined in the income statement.

Based on these calculations, we obtain the following BS map:

Balance Sheet (t = 1)			
Assets		Liabilities	
Cash	3200	Bank Loan	5000
Fixed Assets	8000	Equity	
		Capital	5000
		Reserves	0
		Net Income	1200
	11200		11200

As might be expected, this BS map also obeys the fundamental balance sheet equation:

$$A_1 = D_1 + E_1$$

We can also verify that the change in Assets and the change in Equity are equal to the Net Income:

$$A_1 = A_0 + NI_1$$

$$E_1 = E_0 + NI_1$$

From the Equity value, we can define two values for the quotas (or shares): the nominal value and the book value.

The nominal value, denoted by V_n , is equal to the value of the capital item divided by the number of shares:

$$V_n = \frac{CP}{nc} = \frac{5000}{2} = 2500 \text{ € / share}$$

The book value, denoted by V_c , is equal to the total value of the Equity divided by the number of shares:

$$V_c = \frac{E_1}{nc} = \frac{6200}{2} = 3100 \text{ € / share}$$

The book value, V_c , is often taken to be the value at which shareholders can sell their shares, but it corresponds only to the amount they would receive if the company were liquidated and its debts paid.

The value at which the shares can be traded is called the market value, V_m .

Suppose the company's growth prospects are positive. In that case, V_m may be much higher than V_c because it reflects the present value of the benefits the company will generate in the future, which can be calculated using an NPV.

Profitability Ratios

The profitability ratios we consider in this study measure the relative changes in assets and Equity.

From the Asset variation, we define the Return On Assets (ROA):

$$ROA = \frac{A_1 - A_0}{A_0} = \frac{NI_1}{A_0} = \frac{1200}{10000} = 0.12 \quad (12\%)$$

Based on the variation in Equity, we define the Return On Equity (ROE):

$$ROE = \frac{E_1 - E_0}{E_0} = \frac{NI_1}{E_0} = \frac{1200}{5000} = 0.24 \quad (24\%)$$

To characterize the company's level of indebtedness, we can use the Debt Ratio (DR), which measures the proportion of assets financed by debt.

In our example, the initial DR is:

$$DR_0 = \frac{D_0}{A_0} = \frac{5000}{10000} = 0.5$$

After evaluating the results of the first year, the DR has the following value:

$$DR_1 = \frac{D_1}{A_1} = \frac{5000}{11200} = 0.45$$

The DR of companies in a given economic sector has reference values considered acceptable. DR measures the degree of leverage and therefore serves as an indicator of the operating financial risk to which a company is exposed.

To clarify the influence of DR on the company's results, let us analyze what would happen if DR_0 were 0.75. In this case, the initial debt would have to be $D_0 = € 7500$, and the initial value of Equity would be $E_0 = € 2500$. For the same amount of operating results, we would now have to pay € 750 in interest, and the net Income would be:

$$\begin{aligned} NI &= (EBIT - Int) \times (1 - t) \\ &= (2000 - 750) \times 0.8 = € 1000 \end{aligned}$$

So, the NI would be lower, but the profitability ratios would be:

$$\begin{aligned} ROA &= \frac{NI_1}{A_0} = \frac{1000}{10000} = 0.10 \quad (10\%) \\ ROE &= \frac{NI_1}{E_0} = \frac{1000}{2500} = 0.40 \quad (40\%) \end{aligned}$$

The ROA decreases because NI decreases due to additional interest expenses, but ROE almost doubles because Equity is half its initial value.

This situation can be interpreted as advantageous for the shareholder because it increases the return on its Capital, but the risk is now higher. Debt charges have increased by 50%, increasing the company's risk of bankruptcy. Unforeseen events could render the profits generated insufficient to pay the loan interest.

Dividend payment

Next, to illustrate the effect of shareholders withdrawing money from the company, let us assume that the company's ideal DR level is 50%.

The money withdrawn from the company to be distributed to shareholders is called dividends.

Just as the DR should ideally be stable, the fraction of results generated that are distributed will likely be predictable. This fraction is called the Payout Ratio (P), and we will assume for our example a value of $P = 0.75$.

Under these conditions, the value of dividends is assessed as shown below:

$$DIV_1 = P \times NI_1 = 0.75 \times 1200 = \text{€ } 900$$

Moreover, the value of Reserves, after the distribution of dividends, will be:

$$Reserves_1^* = NI_1 - DIV_1 = \text{€ } 300$$

The remaining NI is recorded in Reserves, and the Net Income item is set to zero.

The value of the Equity, after the distribution of dividends, is evaluated as:

$$E_1^* = E_1 - DIV_1 = 6200 - 900 = \text{€ } 5300$$

As assets have increased, the company can acquire more debt to restore the ideal Debt Ratio. The relationship between the initial debt D_0 and the initial Equity E_0 is related to the DR as shown below:

$$\frac{D_0}{E_0} = \frac{DR}{1 - DR} = \frac{0.5}{1 - 0.5} = 1$$

Adopting this relationship for the conditions following the distribution of dividends, we obtain:

$$\frac{D_1^*}{E_1^*} = 1 \Rightarrow D_1^* = E_1^* = \text{€ } 5300 \Rightarrow \Delta D_1^* = \text{€ } 300$$

In other words, the company does not need to repay any of the previous loan and can apply for another loan, now worth € 300.

After distributing the dividends and receiving the money from the new loan, the Cash value will be:

$$Cash_1^* = 3200 - 900 + 300 = \text{€ } 2600$$

With these values, we can redo the reference Balance Sheet for the beginning of the following year, as shown below:

Balance Sheet (t = 1*)			
Assets		Liabilities	
Cash	2600	Bank Loan	5300
Fixed Assets	8000	Equity	
		Capital	5000
		Reserves	300
		Net Income	0
(DR = 0.5)	10600		10600

6.4 Valuation of Companies

When the project involves the creation or acquisition of a company, we generally assume that the duration is unlimited. Companies also have a limited duration if they go bankrupt or if their shareholders decide to end the business for any other reason. However, at least as long as the business runs smoothly, no plans are made to end the activity.

Companies are created without a predictable end, so their cash flows may extend to infinity. In these cases, the value of a company for which it could be traded is usually calculated as the Present Value of its cash flows, split into two parts.

Predictions play a significant role in company valuation. We consider a time interval H during which we can make predictions about the company's operating conditions and, therefore, the cash flows generated. After interval H , we make predictions about the business growth, highlighting the forward-looking nature of valuation.

In mathematical terms, we start with an elementary representation of discounting cash flows, namely, the sum of the Present Value of each cash flow from 1 to infinity. Then we split the set, isolating the first H terms (e.g. [5]).

In the set of terms after H , we make a referential change, placing the present time in H . In this way, we first evaluate the present value of these terms at time H , and then discount them to the present. This is illustrated in the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 PV &= \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \\
 &= \sum_{t=1}^H \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=H+1}^{\infty} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \\
 &= \sum_{t=1}^H \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{1}{(1+r)^H} \sum_{t=H+1}^{\infty} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^{t-H}} \\
 &= PV(C_t : t=1, \dots, H) + PV(PV_H) \\
 PV &= \frac{C_1}{1+r} + \frac{C_2}{(1+r)^2} + \dots + \frac{C_H}{(1+r)^H} + \frac{PV_H}{(1+r)^H}
 \end{aligned}$$

The available cash flow, to use in this calculation, is equal to the profits subtracted from the net investment (total investment expenses less depreciation). Thus, it is assumed that investments to replace existing assets are covered by depreciation and that net investments serve to promote growth.

To illustrate some of the procedures involved in evaluating this type of project, we use two examples. In the first example, we consider a company that is evaluating the possibility of acquiring another company's capital. In the second example, we analyze a project to create a company, detailing the evolution of its client portfolio and the cash flows it will generate.

Case Study 2

Company A plans to buy Company B and, in order to determine its present value, made the predictions shown in the following table (adapted from [5]).

The data shows that, due to the rapid expansion planned for the first six years, the cash flow available to company A is negative, because the additional investment required exceeds the expected profits of B.

Growth begins at a high rate of 20% and then decreases in two stages to a moderate long-run growth rate of 6%.

Year	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Assets	10	12	14.4	17.28	20.74	23.43	26.47	28.05	29.73
Profits	1.2	1.44	1.73	2.07	2.49	2.81	3.18	3.36	3.57
Net Invest.	2	2.4	2.88	3.46	2.69	3.04	1.59	1.68	1.78
CF	-0.8	-0.96	-1.15	-1.39	-0.2	-0.23	1.59	1.68	1.79
g(%)	20	20	20	20	13	13	6	6	6

The opportunity cost of capital, appropriate to the business risk, is 10%.

We intend to assess the present value of company B, considering a present value on the horizon based on a long-term growth rate of 6%.

The next figure is intended to illustrate that the company with average assets A_t , during year t generates profits Π_t . In the transition from year t to year $t + 1$, the profits generated are divided into two parts: the Inv_t portion retained in the company for investment, and the CF_t portion distributed to shareholders (i.e., to company A).

In the initial phase, cash flows are negative because company A wants to acquire company B's assets, but B's results are insufficient to sustain that growth, so it is necessary to invest in B.

The desired value of assets for the next year is given by:

$$A_{t+1} = A_t (1 + g_t)$$

The necessary investment is defined based on the following relationship:

$$Inv_t = A_{t+1} - A_t$$

Moreover, the resulting cash flow will be:

$$CF_t = \Pi_t - Inv_t$$

The predictions presented in the previous table were constructed under the assumption that profits are proportional to asset value. Under these conditions, if assets grow at a rate g , then profits also grow at that rate. In addition, in stationary conditions, if the payout is constant, cash flows also grow at the same rate.

Under the given conditions, the Present Value of the project can be assessed in a step-by-step manner. This process involves evaluating the present value of the first eight cash flows and then considering the evolution of cash flows from $t = 9$ to determine the value on the horizon.

$$\begin{aligned} PV &= \sum_{t=1}^8 \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} + \sum_{t=9}^{\infty} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} \\ &= \sum_{t=1}^8 \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^t} + \frac{1}{(1+r)^8} \sum_{t=9}^{\infty} \frac{C_t}{(1+r)^{t-8}} \\ &= PV_{1-8} + PV(PV_8) \end{aligned}$$

The present value of the first eight cash flows can be evaluated directly using the values presented in the previous table, as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} PV_{1-8} &= -\frac{0.80}{1.1} - \frac{0.96}{1.1^2} - \frac{1.15}{1.1^3} - \frac{1.39}{1.1^4} - \frac{0.20}{1.1^5} - \frac{0.23}{1.1^6} + \frac{1.59}{1.1^7} + \frac{1.68}{1.1^8} \\ &= -1.988 \text{ M€} \end{aligned}$$

To assess the value on the horizon, we consider the evolution of cash flows from $t = 9$, as illustrated in the following figure.

The value on the horizon, at $t = 8$, is defined from the present value at $t = 8$, assuming that cash flows grow, from $t = 9$, as in an increasing perpetuity. In these conditions, we obtain:

$$PV_8 = \frac{CF_9}{r - g_9} = \frac{1.79}{0.1 - 0.06} = 44.75 \text{ M€}$$

The present value of the value on the horizon will then be:

$$PV(PV_8) = \frac{44.75}{1.1^8} = 20.876 \text{ M€}$$

Thus, the present value of company B will be:

$$PV(B) = -1.988 + 20.876 = 18.888 \text{ M€}$$

Case Study 3

The partners of a newly formed company decided to purchase the facilities of an inactive plant for 200 k€. Conversion costs are estimated at 100 k€. The business conditions state that the company will have to make available 25% of the acquisition cost immediately, a 25% installment in 3 months, and the remaining 50% in 6 months. In addition, 50% of the conversion costs should be made available within 6 months, and the remainder within a year.

a) Considering that the effective annual discount rate for future payments is 7.5%, we want to determine the Present Value of all payments that the company will have to make.

The set of future payments that the company has to make is represented in the following figure:

To assess the Present Value of these cash flows, we can use the annual effective discount rate, based on the time in years, or the quarterly discount rate, based on the time in quarters.

We illustrate first the calculation using the quarterly rate. In this case, we can define the nominal quarterly capitalization rate, as shown below:

$$\left(1 + \frac{r_4}{4}\right)^4 = 1 + r \rightarrow r_4 = 4\left(\left(1 + r\right)^{1/4} - 1\right) = 4\left(1.075^{0.25} - 1\right) = 0.07298$$

As the nominal rate r_4 is the annualized quarterly rate, the quarterly rate is given by:

$$\frac{r_4}{4} = \frac{0.07298}{4} = 0.01824$$

The Present Value of future payments can then be assessed, as shown below:

$$PV = 50 + \frac{50}{1.01824} + \frac{150}{1.01824^2} + \frac{50}{1.01824^4} = 290.29 \text{ k€}$$

The same result can be obtained using the effective rate, as shown below:

$$PV = 50 + \frac{50}{1.075^{0.25}} + \frac{150}{1.075^{0.5}} + \frac{50}{1.075} = 290.29 \text{ k€}$$

b) The company is negotiating a contract with a potential customer that, if it materializes, will generate a cash flow at the end of the first year of activity (two years from now) of 10 k€.

It is also expected that cash flows will grow at a 5% rate in the following years. Given a 15% discount rate, we want to evaluate the present value of these cash flows.

The first cash flow occurs at $t = 2$; it has the value $C = 10 \text{ k€}$, and the subsequent ones form a geometric progression with ratio $1 + g = 1.05$. As this set of cash flows is in an increasing perpetuity, it has an equivalent value at $t = 1$ that can be evaluated using the following expression:

Since the opportunity cost of capital is 15%, we obtain:

$$PV_1 = \frac{10}{0.15 - 0.05} = 100 \text{ k€}$$

The Present Value of the contract is obtained by discounting the value of PV_1 :

$$PV = \frac{PV_1}{1 + r} = \frac{100}{1.15} = 86.96 \text{ k€}$$

c) A study by a consulting firm reveals that the company will be able to enter into an identical contract each year for the first 12 years (equal initial cash flow and growth rate). Under these conditions, we want to determine the Present Value of the cash flows generated by all contracts.

As we have 12 identical contracts, each can be replaced by an equivalent value in the instant before its first cash flow.

We saw earlier that the first contract has an equivalent value of 100 k€ in $t = 1$, and therefore, the second contract, which starts a year later, will have an equivalent value of 100 k€ in $t = 2$, and so on, until $t = 12$, which will have an equivalent value of 100 k€ in $t = 12$, as shown in the following figure:

In these conditions, the Present Value of the 12 contracts can be assessed considering an annuity of 100 k€, for 12 years:

$$PV = 100 \times \frac{1.15^{12} - 1}{1.15^{12} \times 0.15} = 542.06 \text{ k€}$$

d) The same study reveals that the growth rate of Cash Flows will decrease to 3% after the 5th year of activity. Under these conditions, we want to know the new Present Value of the cash flows of the first contract.

As the first year of activity leads to a cash flow C at $t = 2$, the 5th year of activity leads to the cash flow $C(1+g)^4$, with $g = 0.05$, at $t = 6$. Then the growth rate changes to $g_6 = 0.03$, and the cash-flow of the sixth year of activity, which occurs at $t = 7$, will be $C(1+g)^4(1+g_6)$.

In these conditions, the calculation of the Present Value of the cash flows generated by the first contract is divided into two parts: one for the first 5 years of activity and the other for the following years.

The Present Value for the cash flows of the first 5 years of activity can be assessed by noting that the set of these cash flows can be replaced by only two cash flows, which result from representing the finite set as the outcome of subtracting two infinite sets.

The two infinite sets that define the first five cash flows are shown in the following figure, with different colors.

The first set starts at $t = 2$, with the cash-flow C , and the second starts at $t = 7$, with the cash-flow $C(1+g)^5$.

The following figure shows the representative cash flows of the previous series, at the appropriate times.

With respect to the cash flows from $t = 7$, we illustrate their evolution and the equivalent cash flow at $t = 6$ in the following figure.

Based on the problem data and the analysis presented, we can calculate the values of the representative cash flows, as shown below:

$$\frac{C}{r-g} = \frac{10}{0.15-0.05} = 100$$

$$\frac{C(1+g)^5}{r-g} = 100 \times 1.05^5 = 127.63$$

$$\frac{C(1+g)^4(1+g_6)}{r-g_6} = \frac{10 \times 1.05^4 \times 1.03}{0.15-0.03} = 104.33$$

Moreover, the Present Value of the set of cash flows can be assessed as shown below:

$$PV = \frac{100}{1.15} + \frac{104.331 - 127.628}{1.15^6} = 76.89 \text{ k€}$$

Comparing with the value obtained in question b, we conclude that the present value of these cash flows decreases by 11.6%. This shows that the present value is sensitive to the long-term growth rate. On the other hand, as this parameter depends on expectations about the future, which can change frequently, it is reasonable to assume that the present value will vary over time.

6.5 Present Value of Sets of Cash Flows

Sets of constant cash flows

We show next how to obtain the expression for the Present Value of monthly installments, but we consider first the Present Value of a set of annual cash flows C , from $t = 1$ to $t = n$, as shown in the following figure (constant annuity):

The Present Value of the set of cash flows is equal to the sum of the Present Value of each of them:

$$\begin{aligned} PV(C_i : i = 1, n) &= PV(C_1) + PV(C_2) + \dots + PV(C_n) \\ &= \frac{C_1}{1+r} + \frac{C_2}{(1+r)^2} + \dots + \frac{C_n}{(1+r)^n} \end{aligned}$$

As in this case, the cash flows are all the same, we obtain:

$$PV = C \left(\frac{1}{1+r} + \frac{1}{(1+r)^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{(1+r)^n} \right)$$

The terms in parentheses form a geometric progression, where the first term is equal to the ratio of consecutive terms.

Knowing that for a geometric progression, whose first term is a_1 and the ratio is ρ , the sum S_n of n consecutive terms, is given by:

$$S_n = a_1 \frac{1-\rho^n}{1-\rho}$$

we obtain:

$$PV = C \times \frac{1}{1+r} \frac{1 - \frac{1}{(1+r)^n}}{1 - \frac{1}{1+r}} = C \frac{(1+r)^n - 1}{(1+r)^n r}$$

For the case where the periodicity of cash flows, of value C_m , is m per year, the interest rate for the time interval $\Delta t = 1/m$ is defined from the following expression:

$$\frac{r_m}{m} = (1+r)^{1/m} - 1$$

By analogy with the PV expression for annual flows, we can write the PV expression for flows with periodicity m . Just replace C with C_m , r with r_m/m , and n with nm , where nm is the number of cash flows with a $1/m$ time interval. In this way, we obtain:

$$PV = C_m \frac{\left(1 + \frac{r_m}{m}\right)^{nm} - 1}{\left(1 + \frac{r_m}{m}\right)^{nm} \frac{r_m}{m}} = C_m \frac{(1+r)^n - 1}{(1+r)^n \frac{r_m}{m}}$$

Sets of growing cash flows

Here, we show how to evaluate the Present Value of a set of growing cash flows, starting with the Present Value of a set of perpetual growing cash flows.

Consider a set of cash flows such that at the end of the first year, the cash flow has a value C , and the following ones grow at the rate g , as shown in the following figure:

Considering the discount rate r , the Present Value of this set of cash flows can be defined using the following expression:

$$PV = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{C(1+g)^{i-1}}{(1+r)^i} = \frac{C}{1+r} + \frac{C(1+g)}{(1+r)^2} + \frac{C(1+g)^2}{(1+r)^3} + \frac{C(1+g)^3}{(1+r)^4} + \dots$$

Noting that the terms are in geometric progression, with a_1 and ρ defined as shown below:

$$a_1 = \frac{C}{1+r}, \quad \rho = \frac{1+g}{1+r}$$

moreover, considering the expression of S_n , when $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $|\rho| < 1$:

$$S_n = a_1 \frac{1}{1-\rho}$$

we obtain the Present Value of the Growing Perpetuity:

$$PV = \frac{C}{1+r} \frac{1}{1-\frac{1+g}{1+r}} = \frac{C}{r-g}$$

Now, consider the finite set of increasing cash flows as shown in the following figure:

To obtain the Present Value of this set, let us first represent it as the difference between the two infinite sets, shown below:

Considering that the increasing perpetuity starting in $t = 1$, is equivalent to a single cash flow in the previous instant, with a value equal to the first cash flow divided by $r - g$, we conclude that these two sets can be replaced by two equivalent cash flows, one at $t = 0$, and the other at $t = n$, as shown in the following figure.

Then, subtracting the Present Value of these two sets, we obtain the Present Value of the finite increasing annuity.

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